

Agro2Circular

D7.10 – A2C systemic solution model and self-assessment tool

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List of abbreviations

A2C: Agro2Circular

SAT: Self-Assessment Tool

CE: Circular Economy

ToC: Theory of Change

DoA: Description of Action

GHG: Greenhouse Gas

CEAP: Circular Economy Action Plan

R+D+I: Research, Development, and Innovation

DIS: Data Integration System

LCA: Life Cycle Assessment

1 Executive summary <abstract>

This document constitutes the deliverable 7.10 *A2C systemic solution model and self-assessment tool*, an output of the Agro2Circular (A2C) project, developed within task 7.5. *Multidimensional model for adoption, replicability and scalability of A2C systemic solution at regional and EU level* (and its corresponding subtasks). The report outlines the process of generating a multidimensional model designed for the adoption, replicability, and scalability of circular economy (CE) practices at regional and EU levels. It also introduces a self-assessment tool based on this model, aimed at supporting cities and regions in evaluating their readiness to transition to a CE.

A number of stakeholders, both internal and external to the project, participated in the various activities undertaken to achieve this final output. From the literature review to the three workshops and the numerous iterations of the self-assessment tool, a great deal of work has been conducted to assist cities and regions in evaluating their capacity to adopt CE practices.

The report addresses the core elements of the A2C multidimensional model, and how they contribute to defining those dimensions. It's important to highlight that these elements are not fixed, nor are the dimensions limited to this specific set. Regional CE is a complex and broad topic. Through the A2C model, we aim to simplify this complexity and provide a practical tool to help practitioners, public authorities, and stakeholders transition more effectively towards a circular economy.

The Agro2Circular project has shown that transitioning to a CE requires more than a top-down approach; it demands a hybrid strategy involving both top-down interventions from public institutions and bottom-up activities from the relevant stakeholders. The multidimensional model and self-assessment tool created in this project consider these dynamics at both macro and micro levels, helping regions and cities align policies and actions with their unique circumstances.

For regions and cities interested in advancing CE practices, developing a Circular Economy Action Plan (CEAP) is a critical first step, contingent on securing political support. This report and its accompanying tool serve as a foundation for conducting self-assessments to gauge readiness and guide the formulation of CEAPs. Decision-makers should clearly define the rationale and objectives for their policies and interventions. The A2C model provides a

framework for this process, and the recommendations offered within the report can inspire further actions tailored to regional and local needs.

The A2C multidimensional model and self-assessment tool provide a comprehensive yet flexible framework to support regions and cities in their journey toward a CE. By addressing both macro and micro-level dynamics and providing actionable recommendations, the model enhances the capacity of regions and cities to adopt circular practices, aligning local efforts with broader EU-level sustainability goals.

2 Introduction

Circularity offers pathways to achieve more sustainable methods of production and consumption and provide benefits to society. It should be noted that circularity is intended as a means to an end rather than an end in itself, where the end goal is to ultimately achieve long-term sustainable development environmentally, economically and socially (Dr. Rosalyn Old et al., 2022). The Agro2Circular project works in this direction by addressing the need to boost circularity to tackle waste generation, climate change and pollution, providing territorial systemic solutions for sustainable growth and economic development.

In alignment with these goals, this deliverable is framed under the WP7 “A2C systemic solution adoption, replication and scalability”, specifically related with tasks “7.5.1 Multidimensional analysis of the circularity of A2C systemic solution”, “7.5.2 Regulatory, standardisation and political relevant factors at European level”, “7.5.3 Financing schemes linked to the business models generated”, “7.5.4 Governance dimension of the A2C systemic solution model”, “7.5.5 A2C Model construction” & “7.5.6 Self-assessment tool elaboration” and linked with the project objective number 2 “to provide the A2C technological solution the circular systemic approach by building a multidimensional model enabling the solution territorial deployment and its replication and scalability”. In summary, D.7.10 is, together with deliverables D7.11, D7.13 & D7.15, the final output of the work carried out in task 7.5.

One of the specific objectives of the A2C project is to build the A2C multidimensional model for adoption, replication & scalability. This has entailed to build a strong public engagement strategy (envisaged in task 7.1. and reflected in deliverables D.7.1, D.7.2 & D.7.3) and implement effective actions in order to contribute to the co-design and acceptance of the A2C interventions and model. This public engagement strategy enabled us to collect valuable input and feedback, ensuring the model's relevance and accuracy by validating it with key stakeholders at both regional and local levels, as well as at the European level. By involving a diverse range of participants, we were able to incorporate various perspectives, enhance the model's applicability, and build broader support for its implementation across different governance scales. The results presented in this deliverable were not solely the consequence of Task 7.5; they were also influenced by the findings of the Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) evaluations conducted as part of Task 7.3 and 7.4. The outcomes of the screening phase were useful to shape the environmental and socioeconomic dimensions of

the model. In addition, tasks 7.6 and 7.7 are also linked with the model presented in the deliverable, as they represent an optimal platform for subsequent validation and expansion. This deliverable is organised following with a clear and comprehensive structure. After the formal sections, which include the List of abbreviations, **Error! Reference source not found.**, Executive summary <abstract>, Introduction), the document begins with section 3, titled “Methodology Unveiled: The Construction Process”. This section details the seven steps taken to develop both the multidimensional model and the Self-Assessment Tool (SAT).

Next, section 4 “Simplifying complexity: A2C Multidimensional ”, presents the model itself. This section is composed of a brief introduction and a description of the A2C model dimensions. Each dimension comprises various elements, along with a rationale for their selection and descriptions of each. Classifying these elements has been challenging, as each one can influence multiple environments and dimensions. This classification is based on the results of workshops, consulted literature, and the authors' perspectives.

Following the model description is section 5, “Self-Assessment Tool: A Comprehensive Guide” which explains the rationale behind the A2C SAT and outlines the next steps for its implementation. The plan is to convert the questionnaire (which is presented in Annex 1: Self-assessment tool: questionnaire to be completed by regions & cities) into an online format integrated in the Data Integration System (DIS) tool (<https://www.agro2dis.eu/>). This will provide valuable guidance to public administration and control authorities.

The A2C multidimensional model and the A2C SAT are closely related and complementary components of the Agro2Circular project. The primary objective of the A2C model is to define the key dimensions and elements that a region should consider to become circular, especially within the context of the agrifood industry. The model covers eight dimensions: environmental, socioeconomic, governance, policy and regulatory, funding & financial, technology and R&D, standardisation and capacity building. Each dimension is characterised by specific elements that are crucial for achieving circularity. The A2C SAT is designed to evaluate the readiness of a region or city to adopt the A2C circular economy model. It is intended for use by regions and cities to qualitatively self-assess and identify key areas for improvement in their circular economy initiatives. The A2C SAT directly utilises the dimensions and elements defined by the A2C model. It transforms these elements into Likert scales, enabling regions and cities to assess their level of implementation and effectiveness in deploying circular economy policies.

Section 6 “Strategic Policy Recommendations”, presents various policy recommendations, along with drivers and barriers for each dimension.

The deliverable concludes with Section 7 “Conclusions” and Section 8 “**Error! Reference source not found.**”, where the main findings, limitations and future steps are discussed.

Regions are in the most suitable position to detect and address the main challenges derived from implementing a CE, which often require inter-institutional policy responses at all levels. Regions and cities are frequently seen by practitioners as pioneers in the transition towards sustainability, since they often begin to implement changes before national policies have been devised. This is due to their scale and controllable economic systems; their proximity to environmental, social, and economic issues; and their ability to use the local experience of relevant stakeholders (Arsova et al., 2022). Based on this rationale, regions and cities are the primary focus of this deliverable. The A2C model and A2C SAT are conceived as a tool for practitioners and public authorities seeking to develop a CEAP or to enhance an existing one. Nevertheless, the utility of this tool extends beyond the aforementioned target. It may be employed by researchers and industrial clusters alike.

3 Methodology Unveiled: The Construction Process

The Agro2Circular (A2C) multidimensional model is a comprehensive framework designed to facilitate the adoption, replication, and scalability of circular economy (CE) solutions at the territorial level. It aims to overcome challenges in CE adoption by addressing systemic changes across value chains, engaging diverse stakeholders, and providing a structured approach to sustainable and regenerative development.

Figure 1 represents the logic followed to build up the multidimensional model. This framework delineates the methodology employed to achieve the results presented in this deliverable and provides guidance throughout the construction process. The fundamental premise is that the eight dimensions were based on factors that determine a region’s/city’s capacity to adopt a CE. These factors were identified through a case study of the Region of Murcia. Following this analysis (see Figure 2, Step 2), the results were classified as challenges or items related to each dimension. These were then shaped into factors a region/city should consider to be circular. To evaluate the significance of the identified factors and to consolidate and replicate the model, a series of workshops were conducted. In summary, this approach systematically identifies and addresses the key factors influencing CE adoption, validates them through practical application in the Region of Murcia, and refines the model through collaborative workshops, facilitating its replication across other regions.

Figure 1 Model construction logic

Figure 2 provides a visual representation of the stages of development. The process has spanned over 24 months and involved multiple workshops with diverse groups of stakeholders. It is important to note that step 7 is not included in this deliverable, but in D.7.16, D7.17 and D7.18 although it is part of the modelling process, since the replication analysis comes at the very end of the project implementation.

The following paragraphs will provide a comprehensive explanation of each step. Nevertheless, in order to maintain a focus on the practical aspects of the workshops, an in-depth analysis of the results will not be provided here.

Figure 2 Steps taken in the construction process

Step 1 - Theory of change revision

Firstly, to reach a better understanding of the sustainability factors and the framework conditions around CE models, regional context and A2C interventions a Theory of Change (ToC) was performed. This approach attempts to develop a visual, narrative model of the intervention being evaluated, setting out how inputs and activities are expected to create particular outputs and how these subsequently generate the interim and long-term outcome targets (Rolfe, 2019). Using the project's Description of Action (DoA), as a baseline to identify the needs and interventions, several outputs and outcomes were identified (see Figure 3). The primary outcomes identified include a reduction of the agrifood sector's negative environmental impact, enhanced sustainability within the agrifood sector, and increased acceptance, awareness, and knowledge among various stakeholders regarding the CE and the importance of reducing food and plastic waste.

Figure 3 A2C ToC

ACTIVITIES	OUTPUTS	OUTCOMES
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Waste collection, including collection, transportation, storage and logistics. 2. Characterisation & conditioning of organic residues (fruit and vegetables) 3. Development of sorting and recycling, and upcycling technologies for multilayer plastics wastes. 4. Extraction and purification of bioactive substances (small & pilot scale) and evaluation for upcycling. 5. (?) Separation of aluminum for multilayer plastic 6. (?) Ensuring water and energy efficiency through the A2C processes 7. Production of a range of new <u>formulations</u> using the bioactive substances extracted from wastes for their application in cosmetic, nutraceuticals and food (small & pilot scale). 8. Recycling of the multilayer plastics coming from agriculture and post-industrial packaging (small & pilot scale). 9. Upcycling of the recycled plastics to obtain high added value materials (small & pilot scale). 10. To obtain standardized bioactive from agrifood waste and plastic materials that can be introduced into industrial processes 11. Integrate the developed technologies at TRL6/7 through demonstrators 12. Developing a Data Integration System for the traceability of materials, predictive tool & public blockchain. 13. Development and implementation of citizen engagement and community-based innovation schemes. 14. Multidimensional evaluation (environmental, economic and social) of the implementation of a systemic circular economy model for the agrifood sector in the Region of Murcia 15. Design and validation of models & tools to support decision making for the adoption of the systemic solution in the region of Murcia <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development of <u>financing schemes</u> linked to the business models generated & business cases • Analysis of <u>regulatory and political</u> relevant factors at EU levels • Design of the <u>governance dimension</u> of the systemic solution 16. Design of a self-assessment tool for the replication and the scale up of the A2C model in other regions 17. Capacity building to promote A2C circular model tailored to the innovation helix 18. Networking and clustering [for widespread uptake]. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Waste management plans for collection, transportation, storage, and logistics of the A2C residues (agrifood & plastics) 2. Technologies for the recycling of the organic agrifood wastes, and the sorting, recycling & upcycling of multilayer plastics residues. 3. New A2C standardized products: cosmetics, nutraceuticals, food formulations, agricultural films & food packaging plastics (biodegradable and non-biodegradable). 4. Prototypes of the valorised products (both organic and plastic ones) will be produced at industrial environment. 5. Digital online platform Data Integration System (DIS) for storing, saving, processing and communicating the information across the value chain (private section) and to citizens & general public (public section). 6. Circular Economy Business Models (CEBMs) and associated financing mechanisms and integrating them with natural capital accounting. 7. A2C multidimensional model [governance model, policy, and regulatory model] and self-assessment tool, defining key factors of the relevant dimensions for the adoption of A2C systemic solution, and a roadmap for the replicability and scalability. 8. Recommendations for decision making and replication: policy briefs, financial recommendations, action plans for replication. 9. Scientific articles, Project deliverables, communication, and dissemination materials. 10. Training plan and materials for capacity building of all the stakeholders involved within the systemic solution 	<p>Reduced negative impact of the agro-food sector on the environment.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduced CO2 emissions. • Reduced consumption of primary materials (Fossil, Water, Biomass and Metal). • Reduction of waste into landfills • Reduction of water and soil pollution <p>Increased sustainability of the agro-food sector.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase of valorised agrifood waste. • Increase water and energy efficiency • Increase of recycled multilayer plastic wastes from primary production sector. • Increase of recycled multilayer plastic wastes from the food processing and manufacturing sector. • Increase traceability of products and processes <p>Raised acceptance, awareness and knowledge among citizens & stakeholders about the circular economy, the importance of reducing food and plastic waste and the relevance of climate-neutral actions.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase <u>engagement</u> from all sectors involved in the cluster • Increase consumers and citizens understanding and acceptance of circular and climate neutral practices and to promote their involvement • Increase <u>circular solutions deployment</u> and effective <u>widespread uptake</u> [elaboration of policy and regulation, adoption of circular models and financing programmes...] and high <u>visibility</u> of circular systemic solutions [dissemination materials]

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Step 2 - Initial diagnosis: Analysis of the Region of Murcia situation

Based on the previous step, an in-depth analysis of the challenges and barriers for the adoption of the CE in the Region of Murcia per dimension was performed. The information was obtained analysing grey literature¹. The key question to be answered during the research was “*What is the current status of these dimensions with respect to the CE in the Murcia region?*”. The findings of the analysis were collated in the form of a mind map (see Annex 2: Mind-map: grey literature results).

Step 3 - Diagnosis validation

After the initial diagnosis was completed, several factors influencing the adoption of the CE were identified for each dimension. To validate the results from the regional diagnosis in step 2 and the factors defined by A2C experts, various validation activities were conducted with the Regional Stakeholder Panel (please refer to D.7.1, D.7.2 & D.7.3 for more information on the Regional Stakeholder Panel).

Firstly, a survey was conducted to assess the results of step 2 among the Regional Stakeholder Panel. Respondents were asked to rate the validity and relevance of the factors for adopting the CE identified in the previous step. The survey results were then analysed and formed the basis for the second validation activity: a workshop.

This workshop, held in July 2023 and organised collaboratively by KVC and UVEG, with INFO as the host organisation, aimed to achieve two objectives. The first was to discuss the factors with higher discrepancies in validity, and the second was to evaluate whether the challenges and factors identified for the Region of Murcia were relevant for CE adoption in other regions.

Step 4 - Model construction

After analysing the results of the Regional Stakeholder Panel workshop, another workshop was held with the A2C project partners during a General Assembly meeting in October 2023. This workshop was aimed to reassess the validity and relevance of the identified factors. While the previous workshop focused on the Region of Murcia, this one utilised the

¹ Grey literature stands for manifold document types produced on all levels of government, academics, business and industry in print and electronic formats that are protected by intellectual property rights, of sufficient quality to be collected and preserved by library holdings or institutional repositories, but not controlled by commercial publishers. Some examples of the consulted sources: (Plan municipal de empleo y promoción económica 2021-2023, 2020), (Informe del Mercado de Trabajo de Murcia. Datos 2021, 2022), (RIS4 REGIÓN DE MURCIA, 2022), (Estrategia de Economía Circular de la Región de Murcia 2023. Informe razonado de decisión sobre la consulta pública., 2018), (Francisca Sánchez Liarte & José M. Soriano Disla, 2020).

consortium's transnational and multidisciplinary approach to broaden the scope of the results.

Moreover, to ensure a European scope, a review of other projects and assessment tools was conducted. Some examples of the consulted resources include the CCRI-Self-Assessment Tool & “*The Methodology for the implementation of a circular economy at the local and regional scale*” (AIT et al., 2022), OECD (OECD, 2024), [BioCircularCities webtool](#), [FRONTSHIP](#), [Circular Benchmark Tool](#), [HOOP Bio-circularity label](#). These resources were used either as examples to establish certain model elements or to reshape the elements identified in other cases.

Step 5 - New version of the model

Drawing on the comprehensive information gathered from the diagnosis, survey, two workshops, and the analysis of existing projects and assessment tools, a new version of the model was defined. This updated model ensured that the elements within each dimension were clearly defined and fully applicable to various regions and cities.

Step 6 - Validation with the European Stakeholder Panel

In April 2024 another workshop was organised, but this time with the European Stakeholder Panel (please refer to D.7.1, D.7.2 & D.7.3 for more information). The aim of the workshop was to validate the relevance of the factors (framed in 8 dimensions) of the A2C circular model at regional level, enabling the transferability to other EU regions and the development of a self-assessment tool. During the workshop, the participants engaged in in-depth discussions and collaborative activities to assess the applicability of the identified factors in diverse regional contexts. The stakeholders, representing various sectors and expertise, provided valuable feedback and insights that were instrumental in refining the model. They highlighted practical considerations and regional nuances that needed to be addressed to enhance the model's effectiveness and adaptability.

As a result of these collaborative efforts, new factors emerged, reflecting the diverse perspectives and experiences of the stakeholders. These additional factors were integrated into the model, leading to its final version. The enriched model, along with the developed self-assessment tool, was presented to the A2C partners too.

Step 7 - Replication analysis

This model will undergo further validation in two distinct environments to assess its replication capacity:

1. Replication Cases: TECNOALIMENTI S.C.P.A. (TCA) and LIETUVOS PRAMONININKU KONFEDERACIJA (LPK) will utilise the model to develop their Circular Economy Action Plan (CEAP).
2. Workshop with AGRIFOOD European Clusters

These activities correspond to Step 7, which will be implemented following the completion of the model and the self-assessment tool. The results of these activities will be included in deliverable “D.7.16. *Report on potential for adoption and scale-up potential*”, which will be submitted at the end of the project (*March 2025*).

The final version of the A2C circular model and the self-assessment tool are designed to empower regions across the EU to evaluate and improve their CE practices. The self-assessment tool provides a systematic approach for regions to assess their current status and identify areas for improvement. This tool is expected to facilitate knowledge transfer, foster collaboration, and promote sustainable development across the European Union.

4. Simplifying complexity: A2C

Multidimensional Model

In an era where environmental sustainability and economic resilience are paramount, regions and cities face the complex challenge of transitioning to a circular economy. This transition requires a multifaceted approach, addressing diverse dimensions within a territory such as environmental impact, socioeconomic factors, governance structures, policy frameworks, financial mechanisms, technological innovation, standardisation processes, and capacity building. To effectively manage and streamline this complexity, the A2C Multidimensional Model has been developed.

Territorial approaches, which view landscapes as integrated systems of resources, actors, processes, and flows, are crucial for this transition. These approaches address the development of multiple sectors through the involvement of a variety of stakeholders and are structured by multilevel governance. Recognising the territorial dimension is increasingly important in European policy-making, particularly in sub-national areas such as urban, metropolitan, regional, or rural jurisdictions (*European Territorial Trends Facts and Prospects for Cities and Regions*, 2017). These frameworks align with the goals of the A2C Multidimensional Model, which seeks to enhance territorial readiness for the adoption of CE principles.

The A2C Multidimensional Model is designed to provide a comprehensive and integrated framework for evaluating and enhancing the readiness of regions and cities to adopt CE principles. By breaking down the intricate components of the CE transition into eight distinct dimensions, the model offers a structured approach that simplifies the evaluation process while ensuring that no critical aspects are overlooked.

This section delves into each of the eight dimensions of the A2C model, providing a detailed examination of the elements within.

Environmental Dimension

The elements considered in this dimension are intended to describe the territory's metabolism and provide a baseline for transitioning to a CE. The factors included in the dimension are:

1. Efficient waste and water management: the region/city has implemented infrastructures to increase the efficiency of waste and water management, fostering the effective and sustainable use of resources to minimise waste generation and optimise water usage, thereby promoting efficiency in resource use.
2. Waste valorisation channels: there are channels, and these channels are robust, that allow value to be extracted from waste materials by transforming them into useful products/raw materials within the region/city, thus closing and narrowing certain value chains.
3. Territorial exploitation level: CE requires the reasoned use of territorial resources and the control of circulation flows (extraction of resources, transportation of materials and waste) to ensure that the exploitation does not compromise the physical limits.
4. Land and biodiversity degradation processes: linear economy produces cumulative impacts on ecosystems and species diversity resulting from resource use, reducing the quality of ecosystem services they provide. These impacts can be mitigated reducing resource consumption (land, water), waste generation and emission that produce habitat degradation and biodiversity loss.
5. Climate change mitigation and adaptation measures: in the region/city, there are measures to assess and reduce the GHG emissions of the existing value chains.

CE is an approach to promote sustainable use of resources and address environmental challenges. Waste generation is one of the consequences of the traditional linear production process followed in the last decades. The pattern of extraction of primary materials, production, consumption, and disposal, accelerated by economic development, has increased the amount of waste generated (Neves & Marques, 2022). Effective and efficient waste and water management systems are fundamental at regional and local levels. By implementing infrastructures that enhance resource use efficiency, waste generation and water usage can be minimised and optimised, creating a solid foundation for transitioning to a CE. Also, the presence of channels for waste valorisation indicates a region's capability to transform waste materials into valuable products or raw materials, making this process fundamental not only to close and narrow value chains but also as a key principle of resource recovery. Sustainable use of territorial resources is essential. Loss of yields due to degraded environment, pollution, droughts, heatwaves, floods and new pests come at a cost to farmers and fishers. But they are also costly for citizens as they increase food prices (*Sustainable Use of Key Natural Resources - European Commission, 2024*). Ensuring that resource extraction, transportation, and waste management do not exceed physical limits is crucial for maintaining the balance between resource use and environmental sustainability. Linked with avoiding territorial degradation, is the mitigation of land and biodiversity degradation. Addressing the cumulative impacts of a linear economy on ecosystems and biodiversity is vital. The current food sector is the principal driver of global biodiversity loss

and a major contributor to climate change (Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2021). By reducing resource consumption, waste generation, and emissions, regions can mitigate habitat degradation and biodiversity loss, thereby preserving ecosystem services and promoting environmental sustainability. Implementing measures to assess and reduce greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions within existing value chains is critical for regions and cities to achieve the final goal of sustainability. These measures are essential for climate change mitigation and adaptation, which are integral components of a CE aimed to achieving long-term sustainability.

Socioeconomic Dimension

This dimension examines how economic stability, employment rates, income levels, social inclusion, education, and quality of life interact to support or hinder the transition to a CE.

The factors considered are:

1. Business reinvention capacity: businesses are able to adopt and transform sustainably in response to the challenges and opportunities present in the region/city, with the aim of promoting local economic, social and environmental development framed on the adoption of the CE model.
2. Strength of the production ecosystem: overall robustness, efficiency, and resilience of a region's or city's economic framework, driven by a diverse array of industries. It reflects the capacity of this ecosystem to sustain economic stability, foster innovation, and adapt to changes.
3. Professional and technical skills related to the CE: the regional/local labour force is proficient and ready to support and drive the transition from a traditional lineal economy to a CE.
4. Trust in the production system: confidence and reliance that regional or city stakeholders, including economic actors, communities, and institutions, have in the efficiency, fairness, and sustainability of the local economy and its industries.
5. Regional/local cultural aspects: beliefs, values, traditions, and behaviours of a specific geographic area that influence citizens attitudes and actions towards sustainable consumption, production, and waste management practices.
6. CE citizenship participation: active engagement and involvement of citizens in initiatives and campaigns aimed at advancing the goals of the CE.

The social dimension of the CE is only starting to be explored (Valencia et al., 2023). It seems that the discourse on social aspects has been lacking or certainly less prevalent than environmental aspects. Therefore, in the A2C model, this dimension highlights the interplay of economic stability, employment, income levels, social inclusion, education, and quality of life in facilitating the transition to a CE. In a highly competitive world like the one we live in

today, the ability of businesses to adapt and transform sustainably is vital. This capacity of reinvention helps promote local economic, social, and environmental development, aligned with the principles of the CE model. Moreover, and linked with the previous idea, a robust, efficient, and resilient economic framework, supported by a diverse range of industries, is essential for sustaining economic stability. Having a production ecosystem that fosters innovation and has the adaptability needed to support the transition to a CE is crucial to achieve the climate neutrality objective by 2050. Innovation is important, but a production system also relies on having the appropriate professional and technical skills to be truly robust. A skilled workforce is fundamental for driving the transition from a traditional linear economy to a CE, as it ensures that the necessary expertise and competencies are available to support sustainable practices. Circularity needs multi-actor collaboration. Thereby, the confidence that stakeholders - including economic actors, communities, and institutions - have in the efficiency, fairness, and sustainability of the regional/local economy and its industries is vital since high levels of trust facilitate cooperation and participation.

Citizen participation and attitudes are what sustain change. The beliefs, values, traditions, and behaviours prevalent in a specific geographic area significantly impact citizens' attitudes and actions towards sustainable consumption, production, and waste management practices. Cultural aspects shape how communities perceive and engage with CE initiatives. That is why in the A2C model, the influence of regional/local cultural aspects is included as a factor to be considered. Changes of paradigm must be supported by citizens because their participation ensures the necessary behavioural shifts, legitimacy, and widespread adoption needed for effective and lasting transformation. Active engagement and involvement of citizens in CE initiatives and campaigns are critical for advancing CE goals. Citizen participation ensures that community members are not only aware of but also actively contributing to the transition to a CE, reinforcing the collective effort needed for sustainability.

Governance Dimension

The governance dimension refers to the presence and effectiveness of governance structures and mechanisms at various levels of government, as well as collaboration between stakeholders, to facilitate the transition towards a CE. This dimension encompasses the following factors:

1. Promotion of CE culture and trust enhancement: strategic initiatives taken by regional or city governments to cultivate a cultural shift towards sustainable practices and build confidence among stakeholders in the CE.
2. Dialogue promotion in the decision-making process: dialogue promotion between the quintuple helix and representation of private actors in the decision-making process.
3. Existence and implementation of an effective multi-level governance: presence and successful operation of governance structures and mechanisms across multiple levels of government (avoiding working in silos), as well as collaboration between various stakeholders, to facilitate the transition towards a CE.
4. Adoption of a functional approach: strategic interventions designed to enhance the interconnectivity and collaboration within a territory, aiming to create synergies between urban and rural areas, foster community-based initiatives and identify opportunities for industrial and urban symbiosis.
5. Holistic regional systemic approach: strategy that orchestrates, facilitates, promotes, and enables the transition to a CE through a long-term vision and political commitment, encompassing the application of circular models within the government and clear objectives aligned with CE goals.

As stated by one of the participants at the European Stakeholder Panel workshop held in April 2024, “*it’s much easier to change professional skills than cultural aspects*”. Accordingly, the A2C model, as discussed and reviewed in the literature (Kevin van Langen et al., 2021), suggests that effective governance requires the implementation of strategic initiatives at the regional or city government level. This is the objective of fostering a cultural shift towards sustainable practices and the establishment of trust among stakeholders. It is therefore evident that a cultural and trust-building effort is essential for the attainment of widespread support and participation in CE initiatives. The concept of building trust is closely linked with the promotion of dialogue between diverse stakeholders, including private actors in the decision-making process. This inclusive approach ensures that different perspectives are considered, leading to more comprehensive and accepted CE policies.

To effectively build a circular economy, it is necessary to engage in innovative policy-planning with a holistic and systemic perspective. The transition towards a CE must imply active cooperation between different stakeholders, as well as the integration of various policy interventions that will not rely on “silver bullet” solutions or classical work frames of a single organisation (Giraldo Nohra et al., 2020). Avoiding siloed operations and promoting collaboration between stakeholders at different governmental levels enhances the effectiveness of CE initiatives. Therefore, a region or city that aims to be circular must seek these types of governance structures and mechanisms across various levels of government. In addition, as a region, territorial interconnectivity and cooperation are key, with the aim of creating synergies between urban and rural areas, supporting community-based initiatives

and identifying opportunities for industrial and urban symbiosis. All these elements are essential to maximise resource efficiency, support local innovation and promote mutually beneficial relationships.

Neither of the above elements can be achieved without a long-term vision and political commitment. This approach involves orchestrating, promoting, and enabling CE through the application of circular models within the government and setting clear, aligned objectives with CE goals.

Policy & Regulatory Dimension

This dimension encompasses the development, implementation, and enforcement of policies, laws, and regulations that promote sustainable practices, resource efficiency, and the reduction of waste, concretely the following factors have been considered:

1. Circular Economy Action Plan (CEAP)²: existence/publication of a Circular Economy Action Plan (CEAP) and/or strategy in the region/city.
2. Regulatory instruments adapted: policies, laws, and regulations implemented at the regional/local level are designed and adapted to support and accelerate the shift towards circular economic practices.
3. Secondary raw materials market: a market created through regulations and standards that certify recycled materials and valorise waste, ensuring these materials meet specific criteria such as purity, absence of contaminants, and compliance with environmental and safety standards, following the EU green taxonomy.
4. Effective implementation of the existing legislation: the regional/local authority effectively (*legislation is not only implemented but also enforced in a way that achieves the desired outcomes*) implements the existing legislation (EU/national/regional level) and avoids excessive bureaucracy.

A CEAP is a strategic document defining the roadmap and the action agenda to move towards circular systems. Given the great variety of territorial contexts and priorities that characterise cities and regions, the design of CEAPs is place-based and includes circular solutions that respond to local ambitions and challenges (AIT et al., 2022). Therefore, the existence and publication of this type of strategic document in a region or city is crucial for achieving circularity, as such plans provide a clear framework and set specific targets for

² A strategic document for the implementation of the circular economy in a city, region or territorial cluster. A CEAP should identify key actors and drivers of the transition to circularity and analyse the economic, social and environmental benefits and challenges related to its implementation. A CEAP should also consider regulatory obstacles and drivers, and provide policy recommendations. Furthermore, it should analyse the effectiveness of financial schemes for territorial solutions. Ultimately, a CEAP defines the roadmap and the action agenda to move towards circular systems. A CEAP can include several Circular Systemic Solutions. A CEAP can be based on a local/regional strategy on a circular economy or include strategic elements itself.

the transition to a CE, guiding regional or local efforts and ensuring a coordinated approach. Consequently, and despite the apparent simplicity of this concept, it is imperative that policies, laws, and regulations are adapted to facilitate CE practices. Without the appropriate regulatory frameworks at the regional or local levels, the transition towards sustainable practices would remain unfeasible. One of the most valued elements of the workshop with the Regional Stakeholder Panel was the creation of a competitive market for secondary raw materials through regulations and standards since they are crucial for a CE because they enable recyclables to re-enter the production value chain, which reduces dependency on primary resources as a result (European Environment Agency, 2022). Such markets ensure that recycled materials are certified, valorised, and meet specific criteria, promoting the use of recycled materials and reducing waste. Furthermore, this aligns with the EU green taxonomy, supporting broader environmental and safety standards

The last element of this dimension refers to the necessity for regional and local authorities to not only implement existing legislation but also to enforce it in an effective manner. Effective implementation avoids excessive bureaucracy and ensures that the desired outcomes of the legislation are achieved, promoting resource efficiency and sustainable practices.

Under the A2C model perspective, these factors collectively create an enabling policy and regulatory environment that supports and accelerates the transition to a CE.

Funding & Financial Dimension

Availability, accessibility, and effectiveness of financial resources and economic incentives dedicated to promoting CE practices at the regional or local level are essential. In the funding & financial dimension the following elements have been considered:

1. Specific financial lines for CE projects: existence in the region/city of dedicated funding channels or financial instruments established by governments, financial institutions, or other entities to support projects that advance CE principles.
2. Use of economic instruments for incentivizing or discouraging specific behaviours: use of financial mechanisms, as discounts on taxes, environmental tax, differentiated tariffs, by governments or authorities to either incentivize or discourage specific behaviours related to economic, social, or environmental objectives.
3. Adequate disclosure and coordination of funding opportunities at regional/local level: effective and transparent dissemination of information about available financial resources and the systematic alignment of these opportunities. This ensures that stakeholders are well-informed and can collaborate strategically to access funding

for initiatives that promote regional/local development, particularly in the context of CE projects.

Without specific financial lines or funding channels the transition towards a CE cannot be achieved. These dedicated funds, established by governments, financial institutions, or other entities, provide the necessary financial support to advance CE principles and facilitate the implementation of related projects at the regional or local level. Nevertheless, as it is stated in the socioeconomic dimension, citizens are key in this transition. It is not only citizens who affect the pathway to achieving CE; industry and business behaviours also play a part. That is the reason why the use of economic instruments, such as tax discounts, environmental taxes, and differentiated tariffs, is important for incentivising or discouraging specific behaviours. These financial mechanisms help align economic, social, and environmental objectives by encouraging sustainable practices and discouraging unsustainable ones. Finally, the last element refers to the fact that, no matter how many financial resources are available, if they are not adequately disclosed and coordinated; transparent dissemination of information about funding opportunities ensures that stakeholders are well-informed and can strategically collaborate to access these resources. This systematic alignment supports regional and local development, particularly for CE initiatives.

Technology, Research & Innovation Dimension

Digital technologies have been proven to be a powerful tool to support the transition to circular business models. One of the objectives of the A2C project is to demonstrate the potential of ICT technologies as key tools for the implementation of circular solutions. Therefore, in this dimension, scientific and technological developments and the innovation capacity of regions and cities are included as the following elements:

1. Availability of valorisation technologies: existence of the tools, technologies and infrastructures for the valorisation (reuse, upcycling, etc.) of waste and byproducts.
2. Public investment in R+D+I: existence of public investment mechanisms fostering R+D in the field of CE in the region/city.
3. Research-industry connection: the relationship between research and industry in the region/city can determine the impacts in the field of CE.
4. Participation of SMEs in R+D activities: the participation of micro-enterprises and SMEs in the region in R&D activities aimed at the CE can promote the adoption of innovative solutions.
5. Traceability: implementation of tools to improve the traceability of products and processes to foster the CE in the city or region.

6. Availability of regional and local R+D funding: the region/city has its own resources for R+D that are mobilised to foster CE.

Technologies and infrastructures for the valorisation of waste and byproducts (e.g., reuse, upcycling) enable the efficient transformation of waste into valuable resources, promoting resource efficiency and sustainability. Regional/local authorities are crucial to create the adequate framework for its development. Public investment in R+D+I is vital for advancing CE solutions, with strong research-industry connections enhancing the practical application of technological advancements. Involving SMEs in R+D activities promotes innovation, while implementing traceability tools improves transparency and efficiency in resource use. Additionally, regional and local R+D funding is essential for sustaining and expanding circular initiatives, ensuring continuous innovation and development at the regional and city levels.

Standardisation Dimension

In this dimension it is evaluated to which extent a region or city supports and implements standardised practices, regulations, and tools that are aligned with European Union-wide standards and certifications for CE initiatives. The concrete elements are:

1. Creation of standards and norms at the EU level: the region/city actively supports the establishment of European Union-wide standards and certifications for products made from secondary materials. This involves contributing to the development and implementation of consistent regulations and guidelines that ensure the quality, safety, and sustainability of materials and products within the CE.
2. Digital tools to improve product traceability: the region/city implements and promotes the use of digital tools that enhance product traceability. These tools are publicly available and standardised at the EU level, ensuring that products and processes developed in the region can be effectively tracked and assessed.

Regions and cities that actively support the creation of European Union-wide standards and certifications for products made from secondary materials play a crucial role in ensuring the quality, safety, and sustainability of materials and products within the CE. This alignment with EU standards fosters consistency and reliability across the CE landscape and prevents the widespread practice of greenwashing helping to combat public mistrust. Moreover, the promotion and use of standardised digital tools for product traceability at the EU level are vital. These tools allow for effective tracking and assessment of products and processes, enhancing transparency and accountability. Regions and cities that adopt these tools ensure

that their CE initiatives are integrated into a broader, harmonised framework, facilitating better coordination and assessment.

Capacity Building Dimension

Within this dimension, the readiness and ability of a region or city to support and advance CE principles through the development of human capital, educational systems, and alignment between labour market needs and workforce skills is reviewed. Capacity building is an issue of paramount importance with a wide range of different dimensions. The elements selected for the A2C Multidimensional Model were:

1. Capacity of the education system to meet the challenges of the CE: the education system within the region/city is designed to provide the necessary skills, knowledge, and technical expertise required to address and overcome the challenges associated with the CE.
2. Balanced match between labour supply and demand for CE industries in the region/city: balanced match between labour supply and demand for CE industries in the region ensuring the alignment between the available labour force and the workforce needs of CE industries within the region.

A big challenge in transitioning is the lack of knowhow and, as a result of this, a lack of tools and actions. This is why every single member of society should be given the possibility to increase their level of competence in CE. The world is constantly changing, and education needs to respond to these changes (Tiippana-Usvasalo et al., 2023). A well-prepared educational system ensures that the workforce is capable of supporting and advancing CE initiatives effectively. The capacity of the educational system to equip individuals with the necessary skills, knowledge, and technical expertise is crucial for addressing and overcoming CE challenges. Also, one of the identified elements to be considered is that ensuring a balanced match between labour supply and demand for CE industries is essential. This alignment guarantees that the available workforce meets the specific needs of CE industries, promoting efficient and sustainable economic growth within the region.

5. Self-Assessment Tool: A Comprehensive Guide

Getting a good understanding of the characteristics of the territory is essential for establishing a robust baseline assessment, which serves as the foundation for the CE approach. Grounded on the A2C model and all the insights obtained from the different research activities performed (see section 3 Methodology Unveiled: The Construction Process), the A2C self-assessment tool was developed.

This qualitative tool, employing Likert scales³, is designed for policymakers and regional or local decision-makers. It helps them evaluate their territory's readiness for transitioning to a CE according to the A2C dimensions (see section 4 Simplifying complexity: A2C Multidimensional for more information regarding the dimensions characterisation). The A2C self-assessment tool facilitates a comprehensive understanding of the model dimensions within the territory. By using this tool, decision-makers can identify strengths and areas for improvement, enabling them to make informed, strategic decisions to foster circularity. This tailored assessment ensures that policies and initiatives are well-aligned with the specific needs and capabilities of the territory, thereby enhancing the effectiveness and sustainability of the CE implementation process.

The A2C self-assessment tool is designed for regional and local decision makers, public institutions, and CEAP technical assistance. This qualitative tool, using a 1-5 Likert scale, enables a thorough self-reflection on the region or city's readiness for a CE focusing in the agrifood sector. It serves as a crucial first step in decision making, providing insights that inform strategic actions and drive sustainable development.

In this deliverable the tool is presented as a questionnaire (the questionnaire is included in Annex 1: Self-assessment tool: questionnaire to be completed by regions & cities). It has been shared with the A2C regional replication cases (TCA in Italy and LPK in Lithuania) in this format in order to facilitate their feedback and contributions to its enhancement. However, the idea is to transform this questionnaire into an online one, integrated in the

³ A Likert scale is a rating scale used to measure opinions, attitudes, or behaviors. It consists of a statement or question, followed by a series of five or seven answer statements (in this case five). Respondents choose the option that best corresponds with how they feel about the statement or question

Data Integration System (DIS) tool (<https://www.agro2dis.eu/>), which provides useful guidance to public administration & control authorities. The DIS is an online technological platform that solves industry challenges. Using a traceability tool to identify materials, their origin, processes and quality, and a decision support tool that predicts the characteristics of the agrifood residual streams. Moreover, it explores all the available alternatives for its valorisation and selects the most appropriate routes taking into account social, economic, environmental and regulatory criteria. The DIS will allow processing of all data and information required for circular business models and the complex demands of the circular supply chains, being an enabler for upscaling the circular economy in the agrifood sector. The proposed multidimensional model and self-assessment tool are aligned with the functionalities of the existing tool. The idea of integrating them on the DIS will be studied together with CETEC in order to avoid duplications and to better optimise the created resources. Furthermore, implementing CE at a large scale requires a hybrid approach that is impelled both from the top-down public institutions interventions and bottom-up industry activities (Arsova et al., 2022). The integration of the tool will allow private and public stakeholders to have useful information at their fingertips in a single electronic resource. The proposal is that the questionnaire is incorporated as can be seen in the mock-up presented in Figure 4, as one more option in the DIS menu.

Figure 4 Mock-up of the DIS tool and the self-assessment tool integration

Once the tool is configured in its online version, whenever possible⁴, each dimension will be configured with the following information:

- Initial paragraph: Provides an overview of the dimension, after which the focus shifts to an examination of the individual components that constitute each one (for more detail on the dimension definition please refer to section 4 Simplifying complexity: A2C Multidimensional).

⁴ Both the online and printed versions will keep the same structure.

- Element definition: Each element includes a definition that clarifies its meaning according to the A2C model.
- Hints: A non-exhaustive list of hints is provided, highlighting aspects or characteristics to be considered in for each concrete element.
- Likert scale: A Likert scale is provided, which allows the assessment of the status of the element in the region/city.
- Self-Assessment Reflection: A section for self-assessment reflection is proposed, addressing potential barriers, drivers, and actions to enhance the region's or city's readiness for adopting a CE.

The model consists of 33 elements spread across eight dimensions, making it challenging to evaluate the results comprehensively when done manually. Transforming this model into an online questionnaire aims to address this issue by providing a clear and accessible visual representation of the key enhancement elements that the region or city needs to consider. This digital approach not only simplifies the evaluation process but also allows for easier data collection, analysis, and interpretation compared to the traditional paper-based method. By presenting the information visually, stakeholders can more quickly identify areas requiring attention and make informed decisions to drive regional or city improvements. Figure 5 is the visual representation of how the results are envisaged to be presented. The results will be displayed in a spider-net graph, clearly highlighting the items that require improvement or further reflection. In the example displayed, the “Territorial exploitation level” element and the “Land degradation process” element needs measures for improvement, while the element “waste valorisation channels” was rated with the highest score, meaning that its performance is highly effective.

Figure 5 Environmental dimension: proposed visual display of the results

While further work is required, the questionnaire presented in this deliverable is already a valuable tool for conducting a self-reflection on the regional/city level regarding preparedness for the adoption of CE. The objective is to establish a foundation for constructive dialogue that will facilitate Europe's transition to a CE.

6 Strategic Policy Recommendations

In this section, we outline the essential role that strategic policies play in driving the transition to a CE at the regional and city levels. The complexity of implementing CE principles requires a well-structured approach that can effectively address the multifaceted challenges of environmental sustainability, economic resilience, and social equity. Strategic policies serve as the foundation for creating a coherent and integrated framework that guides decision-making processes, resource allocation, and stakeholder engagement.

As Scarpellini et al., (2019), have observed, the contribution of local and regional authorities is of paramount importance in the introduction of and transition to a CE. In order to achieve this, it is essential that the CE is translated into environmental regional planning, with the development and implementation of plans and strategies such as a CEAP. However, this transition does not depend solely on a top-down approach. At the macro level, a hybrid approach is necessary, driven by both top-down public institution interventions and bottom-up industry activities. The Agro2Circular project considers both macro and micro levels in its solution, which is why it is so effective. Therefore, the advancement towards a CE in a specific territory is contingent upon a multitude of factors, including its industrial structure, regional business, level of innovation, and legislative profile at the regional and local level. The crucial role of regional authorities in initiating and promoting the CE implementation, is to establish the framework conditions or to directly encourage local and regional actors (Arsova et al., 2022). The transition towards a CE requires both the support of the government via top-down policy instruments (e.g. subsidies and tax incentives) and encouragement from the bottom in response to changing social preferences.

The foundation of the policies should be on a flexible and innovative governance model able to consider new structures of rules and actors capable of combining top-down and bottom-up processes (Giraldo Nohra et al., 2020). Thus, when developing macro-level CE policies, a systematic and ample understanding of the multifaceted relationships between the different systems (natural, social, and economic) must be ensured (Arsova et al., 2022). The Agro2Circular self-assessment tool is intended to guide policy makers in the understanding of this multifaceted relationships between the different systems, represented in the eight model dimensions.

The implementation of a regional CE is influenced by a number of factors, both facilitating and impeding its progress. Among the most common obstacles are a lack of policies,

regulations, funding, and awareness. Even when CE practices are technically feasible, cultural barriers and economic constraints impede their adoption. The institutional environment can act as both a driver and a barrier, contingent on whether it provides support or hindrance to the transition (Arsova et al., 2022). Key factors for a successful shift toward CE include the proximity of knowledge of material flows, the maturity and diversity of market networks, and established patterns of cooperation within the region.

The strategic policy recommendations presented in Table 1 are designed to be adaptable, recognised that each region and city has unique characteristics and challenges. These recommendations are based on a comprehensive analysis of the eight model dimensions and on the results of the A2C project (Sub-Task 7.5.2, Sub-Task 7.5.3, Sub-Task 7.5.4) and Arsova et al., (2022) research. The recommendations are complemented with barriers and drivers of the different dimensions of the model.

Table 1 Drivers, barriers and recommendations of the A2C model⁵

DIMENSION	DRIVERS	BARRIERS	RECOMMENDATIONS
Environmental dimension	Environmental impact assessments and risk mitigation plans. Regional waste-interchange systems.	Environmental challenges (pollution, slow ecosystem renewal, urban resource depletion). Lack of CE monitoring tools for effective policy implementation in EU regions.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Implement a deposit-refund system for PET bottles to reduce pollution and support the rPET market. 2. Develop and enforce comprehensive land use plans and environmental impact assessments to guide sustainable development. 3. Strengthen waste management policies, including the establishment of integrated and decentralised water and waste infrastructures. 4. Create permanent working and coordination groups for by-products, with a regional register to facilitate reuse and recycling efforts. 5. Promote product lifetime extension through design for longevity and maintenance of durable goods, reducing waste generation. 6. Transition to biomass-based energy and enhance post-separation facilities to improve recycling rates.
Socioeconomic dimension	Policies in favour of key national clusters. Awareness raising campaign and education tools. Better collaboration between companies. Mimetic pressure (exerted by imitating behavior that others have perceived as similar). Subsidised training plans for employees.	Low consumer interest and awareness, prevailing values and norms, and a hesitant company culture operating within a linear system hinder CE adoption. Uncertainty about resource value, weak economic incentives, high costs (including pollution management and land value), and reliance on private funding make CE practices less viable.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Conduct comprehensive information and awareness campaigns, including education on prevention and reuse, to foster a new civic consciousness around the CE. 2. Utilise gamification and innovative communication strategies to integrate CE into residents' daily lives and promote active participation. 3. Establish a permanent forum aligned with national efforts to continuously spread CE culture and best practices. 4. Support initiatives that focus on employment opportunities and the creation of new businesses within the CE sector, particularly involving individuals with limited access to the labour market.

⁵ Own elaboration by the authors based on Arsova et al., (2022)

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DIMENSION	DRIVERS	BARRIERS	RECOMMENDATIONS
		Lack of internal competencies, commitment, and willingness to collaborate within value chains. Price increases are not well-received by consumers, further complicating the transition to a CE.	5. Implement training programs and disseminate information on the environmental, economic, and social impacts of CE practices to enhance community engagement and understanding.
Governance dimension	Institutional environment. Bottom-up approach to policy development. Multi-stakeholder platforms. Enhancement of policy communication and enforcement.	Fragmented governance, lack of cross-sector alliances, limited institutional capabilities, and absence of trust and commitment among local stakeholders and civil society hinder effective CE implementation. The influence of neoliberalism, clashing political priorities, and the need for long-term political support, combined with a lack of a unified policy approach, obstruct CE progress. Deficiencies in data availability, quality, and trust, along with information transfer issues, weaken decision-making and stakeholder confidence in CE initiatives. Limited interest from shareholders and stakeholders reduces momentum for CE adoption.	1. Implement participatory governance models and tools to enhance stakeholder involvement in CE initiatives. 2. Activate public-private partnerships focused on waste prevention and recovery across various economic sectors. 3. Establish information-sharing platforms to improve communication and collaboration among businesses (knowledge exchange, supply chain improvements, and integration of regional bioeconomies). 4. Create regional forums on CE to bring together diverse stakeholders and foster dialogue and cooperation. 5. Develop policy strategies that promote multi-level governance initiatives, utilising regional policy instruments like the ERDF to align regional strategies with CE goals and boost participation in circular businesses.
Policy & regulatory dimension	EU Directives. EU Action Plan for the CE. CEAP Scaling up public procurement for adaptive reuse. Administrative and tributary simplification for the green companies.	Lack of strategic plan about the subject. Regulatory (absence of supportive framework, emerging models for looped resources, need of multilevel regulatory framework). Poor enforceability of legislation. Regulatory (obstructing laws and regulations, lack of global	1. Restructure public procurement to prioritise products and services that meet CE environmental standards, including incentives in contracts to enhance project life cycles. 2. Implement market-based incentives, such as tax reductions for donating used goods, reduced VAT for repair services, and subsidies to support CE initiatives. 3. Simplify and clarify the legislative framework for CE, including regulation of by-products and end-of-waste

DIMENSION	DRIVERS	BARRIERS	RECOMMENDATIONS
	<p>Green purchasing from public bodies.</p> <p>Coercive pressure (exerted by laws and based on a system of rules, sanctions, and rewards).</p>	<p>consensus, limited circular procurement).</p>	<p>criteria, measures against planned obsolescence, and ensuring spare parts availability.</p> <p>4. Apply eco-taxes, such as bonus-malus and an eco-distance model for raw material usage, to promote recycling and the use of secondary materials.</p> <p>5. Align policies with the EU's Ecodesign Directive, integrate CE principles into spatial planning and all relevant policy areas, and ensure a homogeneous regional legislative framework to support regional collaboration programs.</p> <p>6. Provide tax exemptions and loan facilities to recycling facilities to boost their development and capacity.</p> <p>7. Promote pay-as-you-throw systems to discourage waste disposal and encourage recycling and waste reduction.</p>
<p>Funding & financial dimension⁶</p>	<p>EU Funding and Grants.</p> <p>Support coming from Development Banks.</p> <p>National public funding and special budget.</p>	<p>Conflict with other investments propriety.</p> <p>Difficulty to participate in public funding calls.</p> <p>Economic/financial/ market barriers related to lack of financial support for activities related to CE transition.</p> <p>Large capital requirements, significant transaction costs, high initial costs, asymmetric information, uncertain return and profit.</p>	<p>1. Finance the development of new industrial recycling infrastructure to enhance recycling capacity and efficiency.</p> <p>2. Provide public funding, subsidies, and financial incentives to support CE initiatives and drive the transition to a circular economy.</p> <p>3. Create new financial instruments tailored for both public administration and businesses to facilitate CE projects and investments.</p> <p>4. Ensure access to adequate financial resources by establishing special funds, risk-sharing mechanisms, and financial advisory services to support CE initiatives.</p> <p>5. Enhance the focus on CE-related topics in regional funding calls, particularly those based on ERDF instruments, and encourage cross-sectoral project proposals.</p>
<p>Technology, research &</p>	<p>Heritage priorities for smart specialisation.⁷</p> <p>Academic spin off enterprises.</p>	<p>High costs associated with adapting processes and products, increased operational expenses,</p>	<p>1. Foster eco-design through targeted training activities and financial incentives to encourage sustainable product development.</p>

⁶ For more information regarding Funding & Financial recommendations please refer to deliverable D.7.15

⁷ Smart specialisation is a place-based policy approach aiming to boost Europe's innovative potential by enabling each region to identify and develop its own competitive advantages.

DIMENSION	DRIVERS	BARRIERS	RECOMMENDATIONS
innovation dimension		<p>and R&D investments hinder CE adoption.</p> <p>Shortage of advanced technology, technical limitations, and lack of support and training prevent effective implementation of CE practices.</p> <p>Limited dissemination of circular design methods, a lag between design and technology diffusion, and insufficient large-scale demonstration projects slow down progress.</p> <p>Lack of data on impacts and challenges in delivering high-quality remanufactured products pose additional obstacles to technological advancement in CE.</p>	<p>2. Synchronise data collection across national and independent consortia and utilise advanced information technologies, such as remote sensors and AI-powered smart recycling, to monitor and optimise environmental compliance, waste management and end of waste status, and resource efficiency.</p> <p>3. Stimulate innovation in product chains and CE entrepreneurship by providing funding, launching challenges, and allocating resources for living labs that test and develop new CE solutions.</p> <p>4. Implement pilot projects within critical regional value chains to explore and refine CE practices, leveraging synergies with other funding instruments.</p> <p>5. Promote changes in industrial fabrication, support the development of green patents, and encourage the growth of high-tech and clean technology industries through dedicated programs and incentives.</p> <p>6. Foster the use of traceability tools/ digital passports in industry in order to achieve a full value chain visibility.</p>
Standardisation dimension	Certification of products and/or companies.	Lack of standards for actions. Difficulties to achieve volume and standards requirements for recycling materials.	<p>1. New labels for reusing secondary raw materials in certified building or CE projects</p> <p>2. Harmonised certification schemes to support/prove/verify the statements of sustainability of new products and processes.</p>
Capacity building dimension	CE based skills available.	Lack of trained specialised personnel.	<p>1. Enhance the creation of knowledge exchange and learning networks on CE.</p> <p>2. Support educational programmes to train scholars in CE at all educational levels.</p> <p>3. Training and education: training activities aimed at different target groups (students, enterprises, public institutions) to create new knowledge and a cultural background favourable to the CE ranging from low qualified to high qualified workers.</p>

7 Conclusions

Transitioning to a circular economy requires a full systemic change, implying changes throughout value chains, from design to new business & market models, from new ways of treating waste to new modes of consumer behaviour, and innovation not only in technologies, but also in organisation, society, finance methods, and policies. A2C addresses this challenge going beyond traditional waste management, through a multidimensional approach, with a strong focus on public engagement and co-creation, including citizens and all relevant stakeholders in the process towards circularity. A2C addresses systematically all the factors hampering the implementation of circular solutions through the analysis of eight dimensions composed of elements, considered key enablers to achieve a CE. As detailed in the deliverable, one of the primary objectives of the project was to equip A2C with a systematic approach and the requisite tools for achieving circularity and territorial deployment, replication, and scalability; this is the *raison d'être* of the multidimensional model and the self-assessment tool (SAT).

A2C project has been designed to boost the territorial development of circular solutions by providing tools and knowledge about how to implement these solutions. The project activities related to this task (T.7.5) and deliverable (D.7.10) have been focused on systematically identifying, analysing and addressing, through a multidimensional approach and involving all relevant actors, the needs and barriers hampering the development of circular solutions, delivering the A2C multidimensional model. The A2C model and the A2C SAT will significantly contribute to the more effective development of circular solutions by facilitating knowledge transfer between territorial clusters. It provides a comprehensive framework that identifies the critical dimensions and elements necessary for a region/city to become circular, specifically tailored to the agrifood industry. By utilising the A2C SAT, regions and cities can assess their readiness and identify gaps in their circular economy initiatives, enabling them to pinpoint areas for improvement. This process encourages the exchange of best practices, insights, and strategies among different clusters, fostering collaboration and learning. As a result, territorial clusters can adapt successful circular

solutions to their unique contexts, accelerating the adoption of circular economy principles and driving sustainable development across regions/ cities.

Throughout the process, a number of limitations and challenges have been encountered, both in terms of the model and the A2C SAT:

- **Model limitations**

- Context Specificity: The A2C model is tailored specifically to the agrifood industry and focused on two value chains: plastic and food. This focus may request slight adaptations to other sectors or industries that have different dynamics and requirements for circularity.
- The characterisation of the dimensions by the elements defined may not be exhaustive, but it is representative: the elements included in each dimension do not represent the totality or the whole elements that could be considered. CE is a broad concept, and, in each dimension, additional elements could be included. However, for the sake of simplicity and thoroughness, the elements included were chosen after a process framed on the A2C needs.
- Complexity in Implementation: With eight dimensions covering a wide range of aspects, the model's implementation might be complex and resource intensive. Regions or cities with limited resources and limited skills/ expertise may find it challenging to fully implement and benefit from the model.
- Scalability Challenges: While the model aims to enable scalability, the diverse socioeconomic and regulatory environments across different regions may pose challenges.

- **A2C SAT limitations**

- The tool relies on self-assessments, which are inherently subjective. Individuals' perceptions and interpretations can vary widely, leading to inconsistencies in responses. While experts and stakeholders analysis are essential and very valuable when contributing to complex transformation processes, the subjectivity bias should be taken into consideration and counterbalance by ensuring a wide representation of responders.
- The quality and availability of data can vary significantly across different regions or cities. In areas with robust data collection systems, the tool can provide more accurate and reliable insights, whereas in territories with poorer data collection mechanisms the results obtained using the A2C SAT may not be fully useful or incomplete, which should be taking into account.
- The use of the Likert scale for responses introduces potential biases, such as central tendency bias, where respondents may avoid extreme responses and choose more neutral options. However, the design of each item and its graduation along the potential range of realities contributes to mitigate the impact of these bias while enabling a wide representation or responses.
- Different regions or cities may have unique cultural and contextual factors that influence how respondents perceive and respond to the questionnaire. It must be taken into account that the aim of the A2C SAT is not to compare between regions but rather to serve as a roadmap in the detection of improvement areas of the CE in the territory and the design of CEAP.

The minor limitations presented above are related to the novelty of the model and A2C SAT development and will be overcome by means of their continuous use and the feedback gathered for their improvement. This feedback will be collected through questionnaires including quantitative and qualitative features integrated in the tool itself. At the mid and long term, the incorporation of the feedback will enhance the usability and the accuracy of the model and the A2C SAT enabling them to become referents in the design of actionable insights for regional or city improvement efforts.

In summary, D.7.10 details the process and methodology undertaken to develop the A2C model, including a comprehensive definition of its dimensions and indicators, and the creation of the self-assessment tool (SAT) derived from this process. Our model distinguishes itself by offering targeted insights into various dimensions which have been identified as being relevant to the agrifood industry. It facilitates the assessment of regions/cities to evaluate their readiness to adopt a CE approach, thus contributing valuable information to support sustainable development in this sector.

It is of paramount importance to disseminate the project outcomes and ensure their applicability. Therefore, efforts have been already done to disseminate the model and the A2C SAT. Both were presented at the 1st CCRI conference in Brussels in November 2023. Furthermore, the model was presented at the 7th Symposium on Circular Economy and Urban Mining in Capri, held from the 15th to the 17th of May 2024. Also, it was presented at the Green Deal Event “Challenges in Stakeholder Inclusion in the Food Sector: Addressing Barriers to Innovation” in June 2024. The dissemination will continue after the presentation of this deliverable, among relevant agrifood clusters with a view to presenting the tool and making it available for the relevant stakeholders.

8 Bibliography

- AIT, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation (European Commission), ECORYS, EGEN, Tecnalía, Menger, P., Etminan, G., Rueda, F., Bianchi, M., Fernández Fernández, I., Fuster Figuerola, E., & Maleki, P. (2022). *Circular cities & regions initiative: Methodology for the implementation of a circular economy at the local and regional scale*. Publications Office of the European Union. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/068045>
- Arsova, S., Genovese, A., & Ketikidis, P. H. (2022). Implementing circular economy in a regional context: A systematic literature review and a research agenda. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 368, 133117. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2022.133117>
- Dr. Rosalyn Old, Isabelle Rumpfenhorst, Dr. Imke Schmidt, & Raymond Slaughter. (2022). *Discussing the social impacts of circularity*. Collaborating Centre on Sustainable Consumption and Production (CSCP) gGmbH.
- Estrategia de Economía Circular de la Región de Murcia 2023. Informe razonado de decisión sobre la consulta pública*. (p. 16). (2018). [Informe razonado]. Consejería de Transparencia, Participación y Portavoz, Región de Murcia.
- Estrategia de investigación e innovación para la Especialización Inteligente y Sostenible de la Región de Murcia 2021 2027*. (2022). [Borrador]. Región de Murcia & INFO.
- European Environment Agency. (2022). *Investigating Europe's secondary raw material markets*. Publications Office. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2800/48962>
- European territorial trends facts and prospects for cities and regions* (Ed. 2017) (with Lavallo, C., Pontarollo, N., Silva, F. B. e, Baranzelli, C., Jacobs, C., Kavalov, B., Kompil, M., Perpiña Castillo, C., Vizcaino, P., Barranco, R. R., Vandecasteele, I., Pinto Nunes Nogueira Diogo, V., Aurambout, J.-P., Serpieri, C., Marín Herrera, M.,

Rosina, K., Ronchi, S., & Auteri, D.). (2017). Publications Office of the European Union.

Francisca Sánchez Liarte & José M. Soriano Disla. (2020). *Diagnóstico del estado de la economía circular en el Municipio de Murcia* [Documento de síntesis]. Centro Tecnológico de la Energía y del Medio Ambiente.

Giraldo Nohra, C., Pereno, A., & Barbero, S. (2020). Systemic Design for Policy-Making: Towards the Next Circular Regions. *Sustainability (Basel, Switzerland)*, 12(11), 4494. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12114494>

Informe del Mercado de Trabajo de Murcia. Datos 2021. (2022). [Catálogo general de publicaciones oficiales]. Servicio Público de Empleo Estatal. Gobierno de España.

Kevin van Langen, S., Vassillo, C., Ghisellini, P., Restaino, D., Passaro, R., & Ulgiati, S. (2021). Promoting circular economy transition: A study about perceptions and awareness by different stakeholders groups. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 316, 128166. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2021.128166>

Neves, S. A., & Marques, A. C. (2022). Drivers and barriers in the transition from a linear economy to a circular economy. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 341, 130865. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2022.130865>

OECD. (2024). *Monitoring Progress towards a Resource-Efficient and Circular Economy*. OECD. <https://doi.org/10.1787/3b644b83-en>

Plan municipal de empleo y promoción económica 2021-2023. (2020). Ayuntamiento de Murcia.

Rolfe, S. (2019). Combining Theories of Change and Realist Evaluation in practice: Lessons from a research on evaluation study. *Evaluation*, 25(3), 294–316. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1356389019835229>

- Scarpellini, S., Portillo, P., Aranda-Usón, A., & Llana, F. (2019). Definition and measurement of the circular economy's regional impact. *Journal of Environmental Planning and Management*, 62, 1–27. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09640568.2018.1537974>
- Sustainable use of key natural resources—European Commission*. (n.d.). Retrieved 31 July 2024, from https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/european-green-deal/sustainable-use-key-natural-resources_en
- The Nature Imperative: How the circular economy tackles biodiversity loss*. (2021). Ellen MacArthur Foundation.
- Tiippana-Usvasalo, M., Pajunen, N., & Maria, H. (2023). The role of education in promoting circular economy. *International Journal of Sustainable Engineering*, 16(1), 92–103. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19397038.2023.2210592>
- Valencia, M., Bocken, N., Loaiza, C., & De Jaeger, S. (2023). The social contribution of the circular economy. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 408, 137082. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2023.137082>

ANNEXES

Annex 1: Self-assessment tool: questionnaire to be completed by regions & cities

ENVIRONMENTAL DIMENSION

Efficient waste and water management.

 HINT Which factors determine efficient waste and water management?:

- *There are infrastructures that enable an adequate waste/water treatment (number of wastewater treatment plants, share of the city served by wastewater collection infrastructures);*
- *Water is effectively reused (amount of water that is reused and not given back to the environment, over the maximum of water that is allowed to be reused by law) in irrigation and other purposes;*
- *Effective collection of waste that enables valorisation: there are channels and services for separated collection of waste, low rate of improper materials in separated waste streams*

Based on your knowledge of your region/city, evaluate its waste and water management according to the following statements:

1	High improvement is needed: The region/city has some infrastructures for waste and water treatment, but they are insufficient, thus considerable deficiencies exist in water and waste treatments (i.e. low reuse rates for treated water, existence of illegal dumping sites in peri-urban and rural areas).	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	Improvement is needed: There is limited availability of adequate infrastructures for water treatment and waste management that limit the reuse of water and the adequate collection of waste.	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	Neutral efficiency: Existing infrastructures for water and waste management, allow the region/city to reuse a significant volume of water and to collect some wastes separately, but still there are inconsistencies in parts of the territory or along the year.	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	Weak efficiency: There are enough infrastructures to treat the waters according to regulations and facilities for adequate waste management, allowing the region/city to reuse most of the water available and to collect and manage separately a wide range of waste streams.	<input type="checkbox"/>
5	Strong efficiency: There is a wide range of infrastructures for water and waste management according to law and best available technologies, resulting in high rates of water reused, thus facilitating valorisation through Circular Economy processes.	<input type="checkbox"/>

Self-reflection exercise: based on your previous answer, complete the following box in order to improve your region's/city's readiness to adopt Circular Economy practices concerning efficient waste and water management

Barriers/ Challenges	Enablers/ Facilitators
Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.	Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.
Measures to overcome the barriers/ challenges and actions to enhance enablers/facilitators	
Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.	

Waste valorisation channels.

 HINT Which factors could foster waste valorisation channels?:

- *There is an understanding of the waste produced in regional/local agrifood value chains and the existing gaps to close or narrow these value chains;*
- *There are channels to valorise waste in the community (as fertilisers, animal feedstock, compost for local gardening) and their performance and adaptability is maintained in the face of disruptions, fluctuations, or unforeseen challenges;*
- *The waste used as feedstock (agrifood, plastic, etc) maintains a stable presence, and is consistently accessible throughout all seasons and territory, ensuring reliable availability within value chains.*

Based on your knowledge of your region/city, please rate each statement using the scale provided. This will help assess the waste valorisation channels status in your region/city.

1	High improvement is needed: There is a significant lack of understanding and infrastructure for managing waste from agrifood value chains (lack of information on gaps to be covered by valorisation channels). Waste valorisation channels are either absent or highly unreliable, making it difficult to convert waste into valuable products like fertilisers or compost. These channels are vulnerable to fluctuations in waste quantity, quality, and external conditions.	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	Improvement is needed: There is partial understanding of waste from feedstock value chains, but efforts to convert waste into useful products are limited and often ineffective under changing conditions. Existing waste valorisation channels are operational but inconsistent, lacking adaptability and resilience to shifts in demand, seasonal variations, or logistical challenges.	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	Neutral: There are some channels for valorisation at the community level or to produce bioproducts (bioplastics, biochemicals), but they are limited to certain wastes and feedstocks and are not consistently accessible throughout the year or the regional territory (<i>due to the seasonality of crops/crops and because there are areas specialising in certain crops, which makes it difficult to exploit them</i>). Their robustness is moderate—they function well under normal circumstances but struggle with disruptions or changes in supply and demand.	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	Effective valorisation channels: There is good understanding of feedstock waste, with effective measures to convert it into valuable products like fertilisers or compost. Waste valorisation channels are well-established and significantly support local sustainability. These channels are resilient and adaptable, able to handle variations in waste supply and environmental or economic conditions, consistently supporting local sustainability efforts.	<input type="checkbox"/>
5	Highly effective valorisation channels: There is comprehensive understanding of agrifood waste, with optimised strategies to convert it into valuable products like fertilisers or compost. Highly effective waste valorisation channels are robust, resilient, and operate consistently regardless external changes, leading the region/city to have consistent and	<input type="checkbox"/>

reliable availability of agrifood waste and a wide range of synergies operating, closing or narrowing value chains.	
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Self-reflection exercise: based on your previous answer, complete the following box in order to improve your region's/city's readiness to adopt Circular Economy practices concerning waste valorisation channels.

Barriers/ Challenges	Enablers/ Facilitators
Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.	Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.
Measures to overcome the barriers/ challenges and actions to enhance enablers/facilitators	
Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.	

Territorial exploitation level.

 HINT Factors that can determine territorial exploitation level according to the A2C model:

- The territorial exploitation is planned for optimising what is produced and redistributing surplus goods/outputs;
- There are measures to reduce pressure related to expansion of farmland, resource use (irrigation water, nutrient extraction, fossil raw materials, fertilisers, pesticides...) and waste deposition (water and soil pollution issues);
- The territorial planning of the region/city enables to satisfy raw materials demand through upcycled/valorised wastes (accessibility of resources and technologies, connectivity infrastructure, etc).

Based on your knowledge of your region/city and the provided definitions, please rate each statement using the scale provided. This will help assess the territorial exploitation level in your region/city for the environmental dimension of a multidimensional model.

1	High improvement is needed: The region/city faces significant challenges optimising the production and satisfying the demand for secondary raw materials.	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	Improvement is needed: While the region/city partially meets resource demands, inconsistent production planning and limited waste valorisation hinder efficiency and sustainability.	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	Neutral: There are enough resources and infrastructures, and these are well planned to satisfy the demand of feedstock (water, nutrients, secondary raw materials), with moderate effectiveness in surplus product management and waste valorisation processes.	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	Good implementation: Recycled and upcycled materials contribute to satisfy a significant rate of raw materials demand, but limited to certain products due to logistical challenges	<input type="checkbox"/>
5	Excellent implementation: Recycled and upcycled materials contribute to satisfy a significant rate of raw materials demand throughout the regional territory, and territorial exploitation is planned for optimising what is produced and redistributing surplus goods/outputs	<input type="checkbox"/>

Self-reflection exercise: based on your previous answer, complete the following box in order to improve your region's/city's readiness to adopt Circular Economy practices concerning territorial exploitation level.

Barriers/ Challenges	Enablers/ Facilitators
Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.	Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.
Measures to overcome the barriers/ challenges and actions to enhance enablers/facilitators	
Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.	

Land and biodiversity degradation processes.

 HINT Factors that can determine land and biodiversity degradation according to the A2C model:

- *Implementation of regenerative practices (agroforestry, crop rotation, integrated crop-livestock practices, etc.) to increase the return of nutrients to the ecosystem and preserve biodiversity;*
- *Existence of initiatives to increase material efficiency and cascade use of resources, reducing the need of land transformation and preserving biodiversity and biogeochemical cycles;*
- *Implementation of land renaturalisation practices.*

Based on your knowledge of your region/city, please select the paragraph that best describes the status of land and biodiversity degradation processes in your region/city according to the following statements:

1	High degradation: The region/city faces significant impacts on habitats and biodiversity due to overexploitation of resources, pollution and lack of implementation of regenerative practices (high-quality compost use, crop rotations, integrated management). Efforts to increase material efficiency and renaturalisation initiatives are lacking, intensifying ecosystem degradation and stress on species.	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	Moderate degradation: The region/city has developed measures to increase material use efficiency and cascade use of resources to prevent transformation of natural lands and protect biodiversity. Moreover, some regenerative practices are put in practice to increase the return of nutrients to the ecosystem. Initiatives for land renaturalisation have been put in place but are incomplete.	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	Neutral: The region/city manages land and biodiversity through land planning, measures to increase resource efficiency, and regenerative practices to return nutrients and preserve soil health, although ecosystem degradation still occurs in some locations. Several renaturalisation efforts contribute positively to recover ecosystem health and species preservation.	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	Low degradation: The region/city efficiently applies land planning, measures to increase resource efficiency, and regenerative practices to return nutrients and preserve soil health, diminishing ecosystem degradation in most of the territory. There is a high number of renaturalisation initiatives that contribute positively to recover ecosystem health and species preservation.	<input type="checkbox"/>
5	Very low degradation: Habitats and biodiversity are excellently managed, through comprehensive land planning and material efficiency initiatives that minimise conflicts between anthropized and natural areas and reduce land transformation pressures.	<input type="checkbox"/>

Optimised regenerative practices (i.e. high-quality compost use) sustain nutrient cycles and biodiversity. Extensive renaturalisation efforts enhance ecosystem resilience and biodiversity conservation.

Self-reflection exercise: based on your previous answer, complete the following box in order to improve your region's/city's readiness to adopt Circular Economy practices concerning land and biodiversity degradation processes.

Barriers/ Challenges	Enablers/ Facilitators
Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.	Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.
Measures to overcome the barriers/ challenges and actions to enhance enablers/facilitators	
Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.	

Climate change mitigation and adaptation measures.

 HINT Factors that can determine climate change mitigation and adaptation measures according to the A2C model:

- Reduction of GHG emission from the substitution of virgin material with waste valorisation feedstocks;
- Mitigation of GHG emissions reducing waste ending in open dumps, landfills and incineration;
- Availability of infrastructures to reduce GHG emissions through renewable energy mixes - among others.

Based on your knowledge of your region/city and the provided definitions, please select the paragraph that best describes the status of the climate change mitigation and adaptation process in your region/city:

1	High improvement is needed: Climate change mitigation and adaptation measures are minimally implemented (i.e. implementation of LCA and carbon footprint assessments in agrifood industry processes is lacking). There is limited substitution of virgin materials with waste valorisation feedstocks, resulting in large greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions from industrial processes. Waste management practices still contribute significantly to GHG emissions through open dumps, landfills, and incineration. Renewable energy infrastructure is insufficient, hindering substantial reductions in GHG emissions.	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	Improvement is needed: Efforts towards climate change mitigation and adaptation are underway, but significant improvements are necessary. Some industries have started substituting virgin materials with waste valorisation feedstocks, though these practices are not widespread. Measures to reduce GHG emissions from waste management are inconsistent. Limited adoption of renewable energy sources further limits progress in GHG reduction.	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	Neutral: The region/city is moderately engaged in climate change mitigation and adaptation. Industries are increasingly substituting virgin materials with waste valorisation feedstocks, contributing to moderate reductions in GHG emissions. Efforts to manage waste and reduce emissions are progressing, although there is	<input type="checkbox"/>

	room for improvement. Infrastructure for renewable energy is developing, covering a significant portion of the region's energy demand.	
4	Good implementation: Climate change mitigation and adaptation measures are well-implemented. Substitution of virgin materials with waste valorisation feedstocks is widespread across industries, significantly reducing GHG emissions. Effective waste management practices have reduced emissions from open dumps, landfills, and incineration. Robust infrastructure supports renewable energy sources, covering a substantial majority of the region's energy demand and further reducing GHG emissions.	<input type="checkbox"/>
5	Excellent implementation: The region/city excels in climate change mitigation and adaptation efforts. Comprehensive measures have substituted virgin materials with waste valorisation feedstocks throughout value chains, resulting in minimal GHG emissions. Advanced waste management practices have virtually eliminated emissions from open dumps, landfills, and incineration. Extensive infrastructure supports renewable energy sources, meeting all or nearly all of the region's energy demand sustainably.	<input type="checkbox"/>

Self-reflection exercise: based on your previous answer, complete the following box in order to improve your region's/city's readiness to adopt Circular Economy practices concerning climate change mitigation and adaptation measures.

Barriers/ Challenges	Enablers/ Facilitators
Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.	Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.
Measures to overcome the barriers/ challenges and actions to enhance enablers/facilitators	
Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.	

SOCIOECONOMIC DIMENSION

Business reinvention capacity.

HINT Which elements could configure or enhance business reinvention capacity?:

- Existence of new circular business models in the regional/local productive system i.e. circular supply models, collaborative consumption, service system model...;
- Regional/local enterprises corporate/business culture is aligned with sustainability principles and a Circular Economy vision;
- Existence of structures that facilitate coordination between industry, academia, finance and citizens for circular solutions.

Based on your knowledge of your region/city, assess your region/city's capacity for business reinvention according to the following statements:

1	High improvement is needed: Businesses are not able to adopt and transform sustainably in response to the challenges and opportunities.	<input type="checkbox"/>
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2	Improvement is needed: Businesses have some difficulty in adopting and transforming sustainably in response to the regional/local challenges and opportunities.	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	Neutral business reinvention capacity: Businesses are somewhat able to adopt and transform sustainably in response to the regional/local challenges and opportunities, but not consistently	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	Weak business reinvention capacity: Businesses are generally able to adopt and transform sustainably in response to the challenges and opportunities in the region/city.	<input type="checkbox"/>
5	Strong business reinvention capacity: Businesses are highly capable of adopting and transforming sustainably in response to the challenges and opportunities present in the region/city, actively promoting local economic, social, and environmental development.	<input type="checkbox"/>

Self-reflection exercise: based on your previous answer, complete the following box in order to improve your region's/city's readiness to adopt Circular Economy practices concerning business reinvention capacity.

Barriers/ Challenges	Enablers/ Facilitators
Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.	Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.
Measures to overcome the barriers/ challenges and actions to enhance enablers/facilitators	
Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.	

Strength of the Productive Ecosystem.

 HINT Which elements could shape or enhance the strength of the productive system focusing on industrial diversity?:

- *Public-private agreements are in place to governance industrial clusters (if any);*
- *There are active collaborative projects between industry, academia, and government aimed at fostering sustainability and Circular Economy practices;*
- *Industry actors are members and actively participate in regional industry associations focused on sustainability and Circular Economy. Strategic alliances and participation in innovation ecosystems are fostered;*
- *The region ensures an excellent infrastructure for its industries and consistently secure access to resources, ensuring highly efficient operations at all times.*

Based on your knowledge of your region/city, assess your region/city's productive ecosystem strength according to the following statements:

1	High improvement is needed: There is very low diversity of industries, leading to significant vulnerability and instability in the productive system.	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	Improvement is needed: There is limited diversity of industries, resulting in moderate vulnerability and less resilience in the productive system.	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	Neutral productive ecosystem strength and resilience: There is an average diversity of industries, providing a balanced level of stability and resilience in the productive system.	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	Weak productive ecosystem strength and resilience: There is considerable diversity of industries, contributing to a strong and resilient productive system.	<input type="checkbox"/>

5	Strong productive ecosystem strength and resilience: There is very high diversity of industries, resulting in an exceptionally robust and highly resilient productive system.	<input type="checkbox"/>
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Self-reflection exercise: based on your previous answer, complete the following box in order to improve your region's/city's readiness to adopt Circular Economy practices concerning the strength of the Productive Ecosystem.

Barriers/ Challenges	Enablers/ Facilitators
Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.	Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.
Measures to overcome the barriers/ challenges and actions to enhance enablers/facilitators	
Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.	

Professional and technical skills related to the Circular Economy.

 HINT Which elements could configure or enhance the readiness of the labour force to support and drive the transition to a Circular Economy:

- Availability of qualified technical personnel.
- Labour supply and demand for profiles related to Circular Economy and sustainability are in balance.

Based on your knowledge of your region/city, assess your region/city's labour force professional & technical skills according to the following statements:

1	High improvement is needed: There is a significant shortage of qualified technical personnel to support the transition from a linear to a Circular Economy.	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	Improvement is needed: There is limited availability of qualified technical personnel to support the transition from a linear to a Circular Economy.	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	Neutral readiness of the labour force: There is an average availability of qualified technical personnel to support the transition from a linear to a Circular Economy.	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	Weak readiness of the labour force: There is good availability of qualified technical personnel to support the transition from a linear to a Circular Economy.	<input type="checkbox"/>
5	Strong readiness of the labour force: There is an excellent availability of qualified technical personnel to support the transition from a linear to a Circular Economy.	<input type="checkbox"/>

Self-reflection exercise: based on your previous answer, complete the following box in order to improve your region's/city's readiness to adopt Circular Economy practices concerning the professional and technical skills related to the Circular Economy.

Barriers/ Challenges	Enablers/ Facilitators
Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.	Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.
Measures to overcome the barriers/ challenges and actions to enhance enablers/facilitators	
Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.	

Trust in the productive system.

 HINT Which elements could configure or enhance the trust in the productive system in a region/city?:

- *Economic actors' beliefs and expectations about the future of the region and the transition to a Circular Economy are positive;*
- *Regional/local institutions are transparent and accountable for their actions and decisions.*

Based on your knowledge of your region/city, assess your region/city's labour force professional & technical skills according to the following statements:

1	High improvement is needed: Regional/city stakeholders have no confidence in the efficiency, fairness, or sustainability of the local economy and its industries	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	Improvement is needed: Regional/city stakeholders have minimal confidence in the efficiency, fairness, or sustainability of the local economy and its industries	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	Neutral confidence of stakeholders: Regional/city stakeholders have moderate confidence in the efficiency, fairness, and sustainability of the local economy and its industries	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	Weak confidence of stakeholders: Regional/city stakeholders have considerable confidence in the efficiency, fairness, and sustainability of the local economy and its industries	<input type="checkbox"/>
5	Strong confidence of stakeholders: Regional/city stakeholders have full confidence in the efficiency, fairness, and sustainability of the local economy and its industries	<input type="checkbox"/>

Self-reflection exercise: based on your previous answer, complete the following box in order to improve your region's/city's readiness to adopt Circular Economy practices concerning the trust in the productive system.

Barriers/ Challenges	Enablers/ Facilitators
Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.	Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.
Measures to overcome the barriers/ challenges and actions to enhance enablers/facilitators	
Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.	

Regional/local cultural aspects.

 HINT Which elements could configure regional/local cultural aspects related with Circular Economy?:

- *Citizens are becoming increasingly aware of the importance of public campaigns to foster Circular Economy practices and are engaging in constructive dialogue about the political prioritisation of environmental practices;*
- *Promotion of citizen science projects and living labs to avoid cultural resistance to change and foster innovation and entrepreneurship.*

Based on your knowledge of your region/city, assess the cultural aspects of your region/city that favour citizens' attitudes and actions towards sustainable practices according to the following statements:

1	High improvement is needed: Citizens' beliefs, values, traditions, and behaviours are totally inadequate and present substantial obstacles to transitioning towards a Circular Economy. Significant cultural shifts are necessary to facilitate the transition.	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	Improvement is needed: Citizens' beliefs, values, traditions, and behaviours pose significant challenges to achieving a transition to a Circular Economy. There are notable barriers or resistance within the culture hindering progress.	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	Neutral: There is an equal balance between the adequacy and inadequacy of citizens' beliefs, values, traditions, and behaviours in supporting a transition to a Circular Economy. It is unclear whether current cultural aspects hinder or facilitate the transition.	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	Weak adequacy of citizens' beliefs, values, traditions, and behaviours: Citizens' beliefs, values, traditions, and behaviours show some potential for supporting a transition to a Circular Economy, but there are significant gaps or areas needing improvement.	<input type="checkbox"/>
5	Strong adequacy of citizens' beliefs, values, traditions, and behaviours: Citizens' beliefs, values, traditions, and behaviours are highly conducive to transitioning towards a Circular Economy. There is widespread support and active engagement in adopting sustainable practices	<input type="checkbox"/>

Self-reflection exercise: based on your previous answer, complete the following box in order to improve your region's/city's readiness to adopt Circular Economy practices concerning Regional/local cultural aspects.

Barriers/ Challenges	Enablers/ Facilitators
Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.	Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.
Measures to overcome the barriers/ challenges and actions to enhance enablers/facilitators	
Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.	

Circular Economy citizenship participation.

 HINT Which elements could define a proactive involvement of citizens at regional/local level to help transition towards a more sustainable and resource-efficient society?:

- Existence of fab-labs and/or crowd-sourcing platforms where citizens engage in developing new circular solutions;
- Existence of incentives (tax breaks or subsidies, prize drawings, funding for communities...) for separate waste collection systems or convenient drop off stations for a variety of material streams;
- Awareness campaigns in order to promote a change towards more sustainable behaviours, circular and climate-neutral practices.

Based on your knowledge of your region/city, assess the level of citizenship participation in your region/city according to the following statements:

1	High improvement is needed: Citizens show little or no involvement/engagement in initiatives and campaigns promoting the goals of the Circular Economy.	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	Improvement is needed: Citizen involvement in initiatives and campaigns promoting the goals of the Circular Economy is limited. While some efforts exist, they are not widespread or impactful enough to drive a significant change.	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	Neutral: Citizens are present and involved in initiatives and campaigns promoting the goals of the Circular Economy.	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	Weak participation: Citizens are actively involved in initiatives and campaigns promoting the goals of the Circular Economy.	<input type="checkbox"/>
5	Strong participation: Citizens demonstrate high levels of engagement and involvement in initiatives and campaigns promoting the goals of the Circular Economy.	<input type="checkbox"/>

Self-reflection exercise: based on your previous answer, complete the following box in order to improve your region's/city's readiness to adopt Circular Economy practices concerning citizenship participation.

Barriers/ Challenges	Enablers/ Facilitators
Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.	Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.
Measures to overcome the barriers/ challenges and actions to enhance enablers/facilitators	
Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.	

GOVERNANCE DIMENSION

Promotion of Circular Economy culture and trust enhancement.

 HINT Which elements could configure or enhance Circular Economy culture and trust enhancement within the community?:

- Existence of spaces for dialogue and practice exchange;
- Targeted campaigns to educate the public on the benefits and impacts of the Circular Economy are launched;
- Existence in the region/city of specific certification, labels and awards that can enhance trust and lead to a more conscious production and consumption choices;
- Existence of an information system and results assessment method: data collection, generation of open data sources, public relevant data, monitor and evaluate targets and goals for a circular strategy...

Based on your knowledge of your region/city, assess your region/city's promotion of circular culture & trust enhancement according to the following statements:

1	High improvement is needed: The region/city lacks initiatives to promote Circular Economy culture and trust. There are no spaces for dialogue, targeted campaigns, certifications, or information systems in place.	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	Improvement is needed: The region/city has minimal initiatives for promoting Circular Economy culture and trust. Some elements exist, but they are insufficient or underdeveloped.	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	Neutral: The region/city has average initiatives for promoting Circular Economy culture and trust. There are some spaces for dialogue, campaigns, certifications, and information systems, but their impact is moderate and inconsistent.	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	Weak promotion and enhancement: The region/city has good initiatives to promote Circular Economy culture and trust (<i>confidence and reliability that stakeholders (such as citizens, businesses, and government entities) have in the initiatives and systems in place</i>). There are multiple elements in place (i.e. dialogue spaces, public campaigns...) that are functioning well, contributing positively to the Circular Economy.	<input type="checkbox"/>
5	Strong promotion and enhancement: The region/city excels in promoting Circular Economy culture and trust. There are well-established and highly effective initiatives, including spaces for dialogue, comprehensive campaigns, trusted certifications, and robust information systems.	<input type="checkbox"/>

Self-reflection exercise: based on your previous answer, complete the following box in order to improve your region's/city's readiness to adopt Circular Economy practices concerning the promotion of Circular Economy culture and trust enhancement.

Barriers/ Challenges	Enablers/ Facilitators
Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.	Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.
Measures to overcome the barriers/ challenges and actions to enhance enablers/facilitators	
Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.	

Dialogue promotion in the decision-making process.

 HINT Which elements could configure or enhance regional/local dialogue promotion for the decision-making process?:

- *There are public-private partnerships focusing on Circular Economy projects;*
- *The region/city stimulates circular value creation among stakeholders, including businesses within and across the supply chain, resulting in or fostering systemic circular solutions;*
- *Existence of a stakeholder engagement plan, which outlines the location and form of communication, contact person and communication frequency;*
- *Information exchange among different stakeholders on their needs.*

Based on your knowledge of your region/city, assess your region/city's capacity for dialogue promotion in the decision-making process according to the following statements:

1	High improvement is needed: There is minimal or no dialogue promotion between the quintuple helix, and private actors are not represented in the decision-making process	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	Improvement is needed: Limited dialogue promotion exists, with sporadic or weak involvement of private actors in the decision-making process.	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	Neutral business reinvention capacity: There is an average level of dialogue promotion, with some involvement of private actors in the decision-making process, but it is not consistent or robust.	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	Good promotion: There is strong dialogue promotion between the quintuple helix, and private actors are generally well-represented in the decision-making process.	<input type="checkbox"/>
5	Excellent promotion: Dialogue promotion between the quintuple helix is highly effective, with active and meaningful representation of private actors in the decision-making process.	<input type="checkbox"/>

Self-reflection exercise: based on your previous answer, complete the following box in order to improve your region's/city's readiness to adopt Circular Economy practices concerning the dialogue promotion in the decision-making process.

Barriers/ Challenges	Enablers/ Facilitators
Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.	Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.
Measures to overcome the barriers/ challenges and actions to enhance enablers/facilitators	
Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.	

Existence and implementation of an effective multi-level governance.

 HINT Which elements could configure or enhance?:

- Governance frameworks that encompass different levels of government, such as local, regional, national, and supranational entities are in place;
- Contracts/agreements are established with the national government as tools for dialogue, experimentation, empowerment and learning;
- Existence of inter-governmental committees, forums, or platforms where representatives from different levels of government can collaborate, share information, and coordinate efforts;
- Objectives, targets, and measures are aligned across different policy areas;
- Monitoring and evaluation frameworks to assess the effectiveness and impact of policies and actions related to the Circular Economy are being used and implemented;
- In the region/city, specific bodies for the governance of Circular Economy exist, guaranteed through practices such as the establishment of “Local Circular Economy Councils” with consultive character, advisory functions, control and intersectoral participation;

Based on your knowledge of your region/city, assess your region/city's implementation of an effective multi-level governance according to the following statements:

1	High improvement is needed: There are minimal or no governance structures and mechanisms across multiple levels of government, and collaboration between stakeholders is non-existent.	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	Improvement is needed: Limited governance structures and mechanisms exist, with sporadic or weak collaborations between various levels of government and stakeholders.	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	Neutral business reinvention capacity: There are several governance structures and mechanisms with some collaboration, but efforts are inconsistent and not fully effective.	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	Good implementation: There are strong governance structures and mechanisms in place, with regular and effective collaboration across multiple levels of government and stakeholders.	<input type="checkbox"/>
5	Excellent implementation: Governance structures and mechanisms are highly effective, with continuous collaboration across all levels of government and stakeholders, driving significant progress towards a Circular Economy.	<input type="checkbox"/>

Self-reflection exercise: based on your previous answer, complete the following box in order to improve your region's/city's readiness to adopt Circular Economy practices concerning the existence and implementation of an effective multi-level governance.

Barriers/ Challenges	Enablers/ Facilitators
Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.	Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.
Measures to overcome the barriers/ challenges and actions to enhance enablers/facilitators	
Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.	

Adoption of functional approach.

 HINT Which elements could configure or enhance?:

- Territorial linkages between urban and rural areas exists as well as neighbourhood or community-based plans and initiatives;
- Partnerships between local or metropolitan service providers/operators to apply the Circular Economy at the metropolitan level are in place.

Based on your knowledge of your region/city, assess your region/city's functional approach according to the following statements:

1	High improvement is needed: The regional/local government has minimal, or no interventions based on a functional approach, leading to poor connectivity and collaboration.	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	Improvement is needed: The regional/local government has limited and ineffective interventions, with weak connectivity and collaboration.	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	Neutral: The regional government has some interventions with moderate effectiveness, resulting in average connectivity and collaboration.	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	Good implementation: The regional government has strong and effective interventions, leading to good connectivity and collaboration.	<input type="checkbox"/>

5	Excellent implementation: The regional government has highly effective and comprehensive interventions, resulting in excellent connectivity and collaboration.	<input type="checkbox"/>
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Self-reflection exercise: based on your previous answer, complete the following box in order to improve your region's/city's readiness to adopt Circular Economy practices concerning the adoption of functional approach.

<i>Barriers/ Challenges</i>	<i>Enablers/ Facilitators</i>
Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.	Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.
<i>Measures to overcome the barriers/ challenges and actions to enhance enablers/facilitators</i>	
Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.	

Holistic regional systemic approach.

 HINT Which elements could configure or enhance a region/city's holistic approach?:

- The region/city has a clear view of its objectives in the long term related to Circular Economy goals;
- The region/city applies circular models within the government according to the “practice what you preach” principle.

Based on your knowledge of your region/city, assess your region/city's holistic approach according to the following statements:

1	High improvement is needed: The region/city lacks a holistic approach to the Circular Economy, with no clear long-term vision or political commitment.	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	Improvement is needed: The region/city has some elements of a holistic approach, but there is limited long-term vision and political commitment.	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	Neutral business reinvention capacity: The region/city has not a really clear holistic approach, with moderate clarity of long-term objectives and political commitment.	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	Good implementation: The region/city demonstrates a strong holistic approach, with clear long-term objectives and political commitment.	<input type="checkbox"/>
5	Excellent implementation: The region/city excels in a holistic approach, with highly defined long-term objectives and unwavering political commitment.	<input type="checkbox"/>

Self-reflection exercise: based on your previous answer, complete the following box in order to improve your region's/city's readiness to adopt Circular Economy practices concerning the holistic regional systemic approach.

<i>Barriers/ Challenges</i>	<i>Enablers/ Facilitators</i>
Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.	Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.
<i>Measures to overcome the barriers/ challenges and actions to enhance enablers/facilitators</i>	
Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.	

POLICY & REGULATORY DIMENSION

Circular Economy Action Plan.

 HINT Which elements could configure or enhance this element?:

- The roadmap and the action agenda to move towards a circular system is defined;
- Key actors & drivers are identified;
- The exiting circular-economy-related initiatives are mapped.

Based on your knowledge of your region/city, assess your region/city's Circular Economy strategy according to the following statements:

1	High improvement is needed: No Circular Economy Action Plan or strategy exists in the region/city.	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	Improvement is needed: Limited or undeveloped Circular Economy Action Plan or strategy with unclear roadmap and action agenda.	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	Neutral: Discussions on the creation of a Circular Economy Action Plan or strategy with a defined roadmap and action agenda are in place.	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	Good implementation: Well-defined Circular Economy Action Plan or strategy with identified key actors and drivers, along with an analysis of benefits and challenges	<input type="checkbox"/>
5	Excellent implementation: Comprehensive Circular Economy Action Plan or strategy with a clear roadmap, action agenda, identification of key actors and drivers, and analysis of benefits and challenges.	<input type="checkbox"/>

Self-reflection exercise: based on your previous answer, complete the following box in order to improve your region's/city's readiness to adopt Circular Economy practices concerning the existence of a Circular Economy Action Plan.

Barriers/ Challenges	Enablers/ Facilitators
Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.	Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.
Measures to overcome the barriers/ challenges and actions to enhance enablers/facilitators	
Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.	

Regulatory instruments adapted.

 HINT Which elements could configure or define the grade of adaptation of the regulatory instruments?:

- When possible, the regulation is adapted at the local/regional level and to the different value chains;
- A dialogue is established with the national governments on needed regulatory frameworks updates when the responsibility goes beyond that of regions/cities;
- Green procurement practices are adopted;

- *Existence of a monitoring and evaluation framework for green public procurement;*
- *Establishment of clear requirements in tenders to foster the use of Circular Economy principles.*

Based on your knowledge of your region/city, assess your region/city's regulation instruments according to the following statements:

1	High improvement is needed: No regulatory instruments are in place to support the transition to the Circular Economy	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	Improvement is needed: Limited or ineffective regulatory instruments with minimal adaptation to local contexts and value chains.	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	Neutral: Average implementation of regulatory instruments, with some adaptation to local contexts and value chains, but lacking dialogue with national governments and comprehensive monitoring and evaluation frameworks.	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	Good implementation: Strong implementation of regional/local regulatory instruments with adaptation to local contexts and value chains, established dialogue with national governments, and adoption of green procurement practices	<input type="checkbox"/>
5	Excellent implementation: Comprehensive and highly effective implementation of regional/local regulatory instruments, with tailored adaptation to local contexts and value chains, established dialogue with national governments, adoption of green procurement practices, and clear requirements in tenders to foster the use of Circular Economy principles.	<input type="checkbox"/>

Self-reflection exercise: based on your previous answer, complete the following box in order to improve your region's/city's readiness to adopt Circular Economy practices concerning the adaptation of regulatory instruments.

Barriers/ Challenges	Enablers/ Facilitators
Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.	Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.
Measures to overcome the barriers/ challenges and actions to enhance enablers/facilitators	
Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.	

Secondary raw materials market.

 HINT Which elements could configure the existence of a secondary raw materials market?:

- *Certifications are in place to ensure that recycled materials meet specific criteria;*
- *EU green taxonomy is followed and applied in the region/city's legislation;*
- *Integration of secondary raw materials in public procurement policies and requirements;*
- *Engagement with industry stakeholders to ensure that market standards and regulations are practical and widely accepted.*

Based on your knowledge of your region/city, assess your region/city's secondary raw materials market status according to the following statements:

1	High improvement is needed: The region/city lacks regulations and standards for certifying recycled materials. There are no systems in place to ensure materials meet criteria such as purity, absence of contaminants, and compliance with environmental and safety standards. The EU green taxonomy is not followed.	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	Improvement is needed: The region/city has minimal regulations and standards for certifying recycled materials. Some systems are in place to ensure materials meet basic criteria, but they are underdeveloped and not consistently enforced. The EU green taxonomy is partially followed.	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	Neutral: The region/city has moderate regulations and standards for certifying recycled materials. Systems to ensure materials meet criteria such as purity, absence of contaminants, and compliance with environmental and safety standards are in place but have moderate effectiveness. The EU green taxonomy is followed to an average extent.	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	Good status: The region/city has robust regulations and standards for certifying recycled materials. Effective systems are in place to ensure materials meet criteria such as purity, absence of contaminants, and compliance with environmental and safety standards. The EU green taxonomy is generally followed.	<input type="checkbox"/>
5	Excellent status: The region/city has comprehensive and well-enforced regulations and standards for certifying recycled materials. Highly effective systems are in place to ensure that materials consistently meet stringent criteria such as purity, absence of contaminants, and compliance with environmental and safety standards. The EU green taxonomy is fully followed and integrated into local legislation.	<input type="checkbox"/>

Self-reflection exercise: based on your previous answer, complete the following box in order to improve your region's/city's readiness to adopt Circular Economy practices concerning the secondary raw materials market.

Barriers/ Challenges	Enablers/ Facilitators
Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.	Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.
Measures to overcome the barriers/ challenges and actions to enhance enablers/facilitators	
Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.	

Effective implementation of the existing legislation.

 HINT Which elements could configure or enhance the effective implementation of the existing legislation promoting the Circular Economy?:

- Compliance with waste laws in different value chains;
- Domestic rules are aligned with international trade rules.

Based on your knowledge of your region/city, assess your region/city's effective implementation of the existing legislation according to the following statements:

1	High improvement is needed: The region/city lacks effective implementation of existing legislation related to the Circular Economy. Laws and regulations are not consistently enforced, leading to minimal impact on Circular Economy practices.	<input type="checkbox"/>
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2	Improvement is needed: There are efforts to implement existing legislation, but enforcement is sporadic or ineffective. Compliance with Circular Economy laws is inconsistent, and there are notable gaps in enforcement.	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	Moderate Implementation: The region/city demonstrates average effectiveness in implementing existing legislation. While some laws are enforced, there are areas where enforcement could be improved to achieve better outcomes in promoting Circular Economy practices.	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	Good implementation: Existing legislation is generally effectively implemented. The region/city demonstrates robust enforcement mechanisms, ensuring compliance with Circular Economy laws across different sectors and stakeholders.	<input type="checkbox"/>
5	Excellent implementation: The region/city excels in implementing existing legislation to promote the Circular Economy. Laws and regulations are consistently enforced, leading to significant adoption of Circular Economy practices and positive environmental impacts.	<input type="checkbox"/>

Self-reflection exercise: based on your previous answer, complete the following box in order to improve your region's/city's readiness to adopt Circular Economy practices concerning the effective implementation of the existing legislation.

Barriers/ Challenges	Enablers/ Facilitators
Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.	Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.
Measures to overcome the barriers/ challenges and actions to enhance enablers/facilitators	
Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.	

FUNDING & FINANCIAL DIMENSION

Specific financial lines for Circular Economy projects.

 HINT Which elements could configure or enhance the existence of specific financial lines for Circular Economy projects?:

- *Financial support (including loans, grants, revolving funds, venture capital & grow capital) for the Circular Economy represents a proportionate share of overall public support;*
- *Existence of dedicated financial resources for SMEs to ensure their access to key enabling technologies (digitalisation etc.);*
- *In the region/city there are dedicated business angels for companies, start-ups/NGOs in the area of the Circular Economy;*
- *Existence of incubator programmes for start-ups related to Circular Economy.*

Based on your knowledge of your region/city, please assess the provision of specific financial lines for businesses in your region/city to support the transition of the Circular Economy by improving access to finance for Circular Economy projects according to the following statements:

1	High improvement is needed: There are no dedicated funding channels or financial instruments in the region/city to support Circular Economy projects. Financial support for circular initiatives is non-existent, hindering the development of Circular Economy practices.	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	Improvement is needed: Limited or ineffective financial support mechanisms exist for Circular Economy projects. There are some funding channels, but they are insufficient or underutilised, impacting the adoption of Circular Economy practices	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	Neutral: There are moderate efforts to provide financial support for Circular Economy projects in the region/city. Some funding channels or financial instruments exist, but they may not cover a wide range of projects or sectors adequately.	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	Good implementation: The region/city has established effective financial lines for Circular Economy projects. There are dedicated funding channels or financial instruments in place that support a variety of circular initiatives, contributing positively to the Circular Economy transition	<input type="checkbox"/>
5	Excellent implementation: The region/city excels in providing specific financial lines for Circular Economy projects. There are comprehensive and well-utilised funding mechanisms, including grants, loans, venture capital, and other financial instruments, fostering significant advancements in Circular Economy practices.	<input type="checkbox"/>

Self-reflection exercise: based on your previous answer, complete the following box in order to improve your region's/city's readiness to adopt Circular Economy practices concerning the existence of specific financial lines for Circular Economy projects.

Barriers/ Challenges	Enablers/ Facilitators
Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.	Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.
Measures to overcome the barriers/ challenges and actions to enhance enablers/facilitators	
Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.	

Use of economic instruments for incentivizing or discouraging specific behaviours.

 HINT Which elements could configure this element?:

- *Implementation of tax incentives for food waste reduction;*
- *Offer of subsidies or financial incentives to agrifood businesses that implement organic waste recycling programs*

Based on your knowledge of your region/city, assess the use of economic instruments to encourage or discourage certain behaviours in your region/city according to the following statements:

1	High improvement is needed: There are no economic instruments in place to incentivize or discourage behaviours related to Circular Economy objectives. Tax incentives, subsidies, and differentiated tariffs are absent or ineffective.	<input type="checkbox"/>
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2	Improvement is needed: Economic instruments exist, but their implementation is limited and ineffective. There are some attempts to incentivize or discourage behaviours, but they are sporadic and do not have a significant impact.	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	Moderate implementation: The use of economic instruments to incentivise or discourage behaviour related to Circular Economy objectives is moderate. Some tax incentives, subsidies or differentiated tariffs are in place, but their scope and impact are moderate.	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	Good implementation: The region/city effectively uses economic instruments to incentivize or discourage behaviours related to Circular Economy objectives. There are well-established tax incentives, subsidies, or differentiated tariffs that are actively promoting desired behaviours.	<input type="checkbox"/>
5	Excellent implementation: The region/city excels in using economic instruments to incentivize or discourage behaviours related to Circular Economy objectives. Comprehensive and highly effective tax incentives, subsidies, or differentiated tariffs are in place, driving significant behavioural changes and contributing to sustainable economic development.	<input type="checkbox"/>

Self-reflection exercise: based on your previous answer, complete the following box in order to improve your region's/city's readiness to adopt Circular Economy practices concerning the use of economic instruments for incentivizing or discouraging specific behaviours.

Barriers/ Challenges	Enablers/ Facilitators
Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.	Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.
Measures to overcome the barriers/ challenges and actions to enhance enablers/facilitators	
Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.	

Adequate disclosure and coordination of funding opportunities at regional/local level.

 HINT Which elements could configure or enhance an adequate disclosure and coordination of funding opportunities?:

- Clear and accessible information about available funding opportunities for Circular Economy initiatives is provided;
- Consolidated information on funding opportunities related to the Circular Economy is available and centralised by the relevant authorities;
- Tailored guidance and support to applicants navigating funding opportunities is offered;
- The financial system of the region/city is well related and integrated.

Based on your knowledge of your region/city, assess your region/city's coordination of funding opportunities according to the following statements:

1	High improvement is needed: There is minimal or no effective disclosure of funding opportunities for Circular Economy initiatives at the regional/local level. Information about available funding is scarce, fragmented, or not easily accessible. Coordination among relevant authorities to centralise funding information is lacking.	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	Improvement is needed: There are some efforts to disclose funding opportunities, but they are limited in effectiveness. Information about funding opportunities for Circular Economy projects exists, but it is not comprehensive or easily accessible. Coordination among authorities is sporadic, and there is room for improvement in providing tailored guidance and support to applicants.	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	Moderate implementation: There is an acceptable level of disclosure and coordination of funding opportunities for Circular Economy initiatives. Information on funding opportunities is available but may not be fully consolidated or centralised. Some guidance and support is provided to applicants, but improvements could increase accessibility and effectiveness.	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	Good implementation: The region/city demonstrates effective disclosure and coordination of funding opportunities for Circular Economy projects. Clear and accessible information about available funding is provided. Relevant authorities coordinate to centralise funding information, making it easier for stakeholders to access and navigate funding opportunities. Tailored guidance and support are available to applicants.	<input type="checkbox"/>
5	Excellent implementation: The region/city excels in the disclosure and coordination of funding opportunities for Circular Economy initiatives. There is comprehensive and transparent dissemination of information about available funding resources. Funding opportunities related to Circular Economy projects are centralised and well-coordinated by relevant authorities. Applicants receive tailored guidance and support, and the financial system is integrated to facilitate access to funding for regional/local development.	<input type="checkbox"/>

Self-reflection exercise: based on your previous answer, complete the following box in order to improve your region's/city's readiness to adopt Circular Economy practices concerning the adequate disclosure and coordination of funding opportunities at regional/local level.

Barriers/ Challenges	Enablers/ Facilitators
Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.	Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.
Measures to overcome the barriers/ challenges and actions to enhance enablers/facilitators	
Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.	

TECHNOLOGY, RESEARCH & INNOVATION DIMENSION

Availability of valorisation technologies.

 HINT Which elements could boost the tools and technologies that enable the Circular Economy?:

- Understanding the availability of technologies, tools and infrastructures for circular processes at pilot scale in the region/city;
- Availability of research/technological centres oriented to CE;
- Provision of services fostering CE to companies by research and technological centres;
- Prevalence of bio-based fine and specialty chemicals (high technology applications) and other value chains that require advanced technology and R+D for recovery, reuse, remanufacturing, and recycling (metals, polymers, and electronic waste) vs low technology circular processes (i.e incineration, composting).

Based on your knowledge of your region/city, assess each element by choosing a rating from 1 to 5 based on the region/city's current state of valorisation technologies and related support structures:

1	High improvement is needed: The region/city has minimal or no presence of technologies, tools, and infrastructures for valorisation. Research centres focused on Circular Economy (CE) are absent or extremely limited. Services fostering CE are non-existent, and there are no advanced technology applications. Overall, the region/city lacks fundamental elements to support circular processes.	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	Improvement is needed: The region/city has some technologies, tools, and infrastructures for valorisation, but they are underdeveloped or not effectively utilised. There are a few research centres oriented to CE, but their impact is limited. Basic services are provided to companies, but they are sporadic and not well-coordinated. There is minimal presence of advanced technology applications for valorisation, with a predominant reliance on low technology processes like incineration or composting.	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	Moderate implementation: The region/city has an acceptable level of technologies, tools, and infrastructures for valorisation, but they are not fully optimised. There is a moderate presence of research centres focused on CE, providing some level of support and services to companies. Advanced technology applications for valorisation are present but not widespread, with gaps in the value chains for bio-based chemicals and other high-tech processes. Coordination and accessibility could be improved.	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	Good implementation: The region/city has a well-developed network of technologies, tools, and infrastructures for valorisation. Several research centres are actively involved in CE, offering a wide range of services to support companies. Advanced technology applications are prevalent, covering significant value chains for recovery, reuse, remanufacturing, and recycling of materials like metals, polymers, and electronic waste. Coordination among stakeholders is effective, making resources easily accessible.	<input type="checkbox"/>
5	Excellent implementation: The region/city excels in providing comprehensive and advanced technologies, tools, and infrastructures for the valorisation of waste and by-products. Numerous research centres dedicated to CE offer extensive and well-coordinated services to companies. Advanced technology applications are widespread and cover all necessary value chains, from bio-based fine and specialty chemicals to high-tech recovery processes for various materials. The system is highly integrated and accessible, facilitating seamless support for circular processes.	<input type="checkbox"/>

Self-reflection exercise: based on your previous answer, complete the following box in order to improve your region's/city's readiness to adopt Circular Economy practices concerning the availability of valorisation technologies.

Barriers/ Challenges	Enablers/ Facilitators
Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.	Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.
Measures to overcome the barriers/ challenges and actions to enhance enablers/facilitators	
Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.	

Public investment in R+D+I.

 HINT Which elements reflect public investment in R+D+I?:

- Presence of public universities and research centres with chairs/departments in the field of CE;
- Level of implementation of pilot cases through public calls for projects;
- Public stimulation of demand for R+D results through tenders, pre-procurement and pre-procurement mechanisms.

1	High improvement is needed: There is a lack of chairs and departments devoted to Circular Economy in public universities and research centres of the city/region. Public demand of R+D results is minimal or inexistent due to lack of mechanisms.	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	Improvement is needed: There are some chairs and departments devoted to Circular Economy in public universities and research centres of the city/region, but pilot cases are scarce and mechanisms to boost the public demand of R+D results are not implemented.	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	Neutral: There are some chairs and departments devoted to Circular Economy in public universities and research centres of the city/region. Several pilot cases are implemented, but mechanisms to boost the public demand of R+D results in CE are insufficient.	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	Good implementation: There are several chairs and departments in public universities and research centres focused on CE, and some pilot cases are implemented. There are a variety of mechanisms to boost the demand of R+D results in Circular Economy, but with some limitations (flexibility of procedures, purchasing criteria etc).	<input type="checkbox"/>
5	Excellent implementation: There are chairs, departments and research centres focused on CE, and pilot cases are implemented by means of public calls for projects. The public sector fosters the demand of R+D results in CE through pre-procurement, procurement and tender mechanisms in Circular Economy.	<input type="checkbox"/>

Self-reflection exercise: based on your previous answer, complete the following box in order to improve your region's/city's readiness to adopt Circular Economy practices concerning the public investment in R+D+I.

Barriers/ Challenges	Enablers/ Facilitators
Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.	Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.
Measures to overcome the barriers/ challenges and actions to enhance enablers/facilitators	

Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.

Research-industry connection.

 HINT Which elements reflect research-industry connections?:

- Presence of private sector-funded chairs at universities to support research on Circular Economy (*the region/city should have partnerships between universities and private sector entities, providing funding for dedicated research chairs focused on Circular Economy initiatives*);
- High employment levels in R&D activities within the industry, with a significant number of advanced degree holders (PhD and postdoc positions);
- The environment should foster the creation of new businesses and ventures that develop from academic and research institutions, showcasing a dynamic ecosystem for innovation and commercialization in the Circular Economy;
- Active collaboration between research institutions and industry to stimulate R&D demand, including access to research facilities and resources, and joint exploitation agreements (patents and licenses);
- Existence of incubators to promote Circular Economy projects: the region/city should have facilities that provide support, resources, and mentorship to new ventures and projects focused on Circular Economy principles, promoting growth and development in this sector.

Based on your knowledge of your region/city, assess the connection between research and industry sectors in the field of CE in your region/city according to the following statements:

1	High improvement is needed: There are no or minimal private sector-funded chairs related to CE at universities, and few or no incubators promoting Circular Economy projects. Employment of PhDs and postdocs in industry R&D positions is very low. Spin-offs and start-ups from research centres and universities are rare. Collaboration between research institutions and industry for joint exploitation of research is almost non-existent	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	Improvement is needed: There are some private sector-funded chairs related to CE at universities, and a few incubators and spin-offs exist. However, employment of PhDs and postdocs in industry R&D positions is limited. Collaborative agreements for joint exploitation of research are infrequent, and access to research facilities and resources is restricted.	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	Moderate implementation: Several private sector-funded chairs related to CE exist at universities, and there is moderate employment of PhDs and postdocs in industry R&D roles. Some spin-offs and start-ups emerge from research centres and universities, but collaborative agreements for access to research facilities and joint exploitation of research results are scarce. The availability of incubators for Circular Economy projects is limited.	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	Good implementation: There are multiple private sector-funded chairs related to CE at universities, and employment rates of PhDs and postdocs in industry R&D positions are high. Industry and universities frequently develop agreements for the	<input type="checkbox"/>

	use of research facilities and joint exploitation of research results. Spin-offs and start-ups are common, and several incubators support Circular Economy projects.	
5	Excellent implementation: There is a wide variety of private sector-funded chairs related to CE at universities, with high employment rates of PhDs and postdocs in industry R&D positions. Comprehensive agreements between industry and universities facilitate access to research facilities and joint exploitation of research results. The emergence of spin-offs and start-ups from research centres and universities is robust, and numerous incubators support Circular Economy projects, fostering a dynamic innovation ecosystem.	<input type="checkbox"/>

Self-reflection exercise: based on your previous answer, complete the following box in order to improve your region's/city's readiness to adopt Circular Economy practices concerning the research-industry connection.

Barriers/ Challenges	Enablers/ Facilitators
Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.	Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.
Measures to overcome the barriers/ challenges and actions to enhance enablers/facilitators	
Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.	

Participation of SMEs in R+D activities.

 HINT Which elements reflect the participation of SMEs in R+D activities?:

- Degree of participation of SMEs and microenterprises in R+D projects;
- Creation of employments for R+D activities in SMEs

Based on your knowledge of your region/city, assess the participation of SMEs in R+D activities according to the following statements:

1	High improvement is needed: There is no or minimal participation of SMEs and microenterprises of the region/city in R+D projects aimed at CE	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	Improvement is needed: Some SMEs and microenterprises participate in R+D projects aimed at CE, but employment in these activities is low and does not involve dedicated teams or departments, limiting the resources available.	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	Neutral: Some SMEs and microenterprises participate in R+D projects aimed at CE, with dedicated teams or departments involved, but representing low employment rates.	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	Good implementation: Several SMEs and microenterprises participate in R+D projects aimed at CE, with dedicated teams or departments involved, but restricted to certain sectors or value chains.	<input type="checkbox"/>
5	Excellent implementation: Many SMEs and microenterprises participate in R+D projects aimed at CE, with dedicated teams or departments involved, and there is a high rate of employment in R+D activities for PhDs and postdoctoral researchers.	<input type="checkbox"/>

Self-reflection exercise: based on your previous answer, complete the following box in order to improve your region's/city's readiness to adopt Circular Economy practices concerning the participation of SMEs in R+D activities.

Barriers/ Challenges	Enablers/ Facilitators
Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.	Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.
Measures to overcome the barriers/ challenges and actions to enhance enablers/facilitators	
Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.	

Traceability.

 HINT Which elements reflect the implementation of traceability tools?:

- Implementation of IT infrastructure or knowledge, such as blockchain to facilitate traceability;
- Creation of ecosystems for circular change in specific value chain(s): systems for verification of circular claims, product lifetime extension, circular business models, etc.

1	High improvement is needed: The region/city has minimal or no investments in tools to improve traceability, and there is a lack of ecosystems fostering circular change	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	Improvement is needed: There is some investment in traceability tools through IT infrastructures (blockchain, digital passports...). Ecosystems for circular change have been created in specific value chains.	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	Moderate implementation: The region/city moderately invests in IT infrastructure to support traceability, but harmonisation is insufficient, and the systems do not cover entire value chains.	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	Good implementation: The region/city effectively supports traceability investing in IT tools in different value chains, and promotes ecosystems for circular change (i.e. verification of circular claims) but there are still gaps in some processes (lack of data, distrust, lack of participation of consumers or end users).	<input type="checkbox"/>
5	Excellent implementation: The region/city makes high investment in traceability systems using harmonised tools and protocols, covering several value chains. Ecosystems for circular change (verification of circular claims, circular businesses models) are implemented in different sectors.	<input type="checkbox"/>

Self-reflection exercise: based on your previous answer, complete the following box in order to improve your region's/city's readiness to adopt Circular Economy practices concerning traceability.

Barriers/ Challenges	Enablers/ Facilitators
Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.	Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.
Measures to overcome the barriers/ challenges and actions to enhance enablers/facilitators	
Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.	

Availability of regional and local R+D funding.

 HINT Which elements reflect the availability of regional and local R+D funding schemes?:

- There is an availability of regional funds for R+D oriented to CE;

- Seal of excellence approaches are implemented providing funding to high quality proposals at EU or regional level;
- Regional entities have received seals of excellence allowing them to access other types of funds;
- Mobilisation of ERDF funds for R+D.

Based on your knowledge of your region/city, assess your region/city's availability on own resources for R+D supporting the implementation of CE according to the following statements:

1	High improvement is needed: The region/city has minimal or no regional support to R+D. Seals of excellence approaches are not implemented at regional level and regional entities have not received seals of excellence to access other types of funding.	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	Improvement is needed: There is some regional support of R+D at regional/local level to progress in CE. Some regional entities have received seals of excellence to access other types of funding but these are not implemented at regional level.	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	Moderate implementation: The region/city moderately supports R+D in the field of CE. Some mechanisms to fund high quality proposals receiving seals of excellence exist at regional level.	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	Good implementation: The region/city effectively supports R+D in the field of CE. Well-developed mechanisms for funding proposals that receive seals of excellence are implemented and European Regional Development Fund (ERDF) funds are mobilised to promote R+D	<input type="checkbox"/>
5	Excellent implementation: The region/city excels R+D in the field of CE, through comprehensive mechanisms to support proposals that have received seals of excellence and ERDF funds are widely mobilised to promote R+D.	<input type="checkbox"/>

Self-reflection exercise: based on your previous answer, complete the following box in order to improve your region's/city's readiness to adopt Circular Economy practices concerning the availability of regional and local R+D funding.

Barriers/ Challenges	Enablers/ Facilitators
Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.	Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.
Measures to overcome the barriers/ challenges and actions to enhance enablers/facilitators	
Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.	

STANDARISATION DIMENSION

Creation of standards and norms at the EU level.

 HINT Which elements could configure or enhance this element:

- There are regulations at regional level fostering the use of CE standards and norms;
- Entities in the region/city collaborate with standardisation agencies in the elaboration of norms for products and processes;

- *The assessment of circularity in businesses using existing standardized tools is promoted.*

Based on your knowledge of your region/city, assess your region/city's support to the establishment of European Union-wide standards and certifications for products made from secondary materials according to the following statements:

1	High improvement is needed: The region/city provides minimal or no support for the creation of EU-wide standards and certifications. There are no regulations promoting the use of CE standards and norms, no collaboration with standardisation agencies, and no promotion of circularity assessments in businesses.	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	Improvement is needed: There are some initiatives to support the creation of EU-wide standards and certifications, but they are limited and underdeveloped. Regional regulations are minimal, collaboration with standardisation agencies is sporadic, and the promotion of circularity assessments in businesses is limited.	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	Moderate implementation: The region/city moderately supports the creation of EU-wide standards and certifications. There are some regulations at the regional level, occasional collaboration with standardisation agencies, and moderate promotion of circularity assessments in businesses.	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	Good implementation: The region/city effectively supports the creation of EU-wide standards and certifications. Well-developed regulations at the regional level foster the use of CE standards and norms. There is active collaboration with standardisation agencies and regular promotion of circularity assessments in businesses.	<input type="checkbox"/>
5	Excellent implementation: The region/city excels in supporting the creation of EU-wide standards and certifications. Comprehensive and robust regional regulations foster the use of CE standards and norms. There is extensive collaboration with standardisation agencies and strong promotion of circularity assessments in businesses.	<input type="checkbox"/>

Self-reflection exercise: based on your previous answer, complete the following box in order to improve your region's/city's readiness to adopt Circular Economy practices concerning the creation of standards and norms at the EU level.

Barriers/ Challenges	Enablers/ Facilitators
Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.	Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.
Measures to overcome the barriers/ challenges and actions to enhance enablers/facilitators	
Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.	

Digital tools to improve product traceability.

 HINT Which elements could configure or enhance the use of digital tools to improve product traceability:

- *Industries in the region/city uses public digital passports at EU level;*
- *Availability of public digital passports in the region for traceability, interoperable with EU standards.*

Based on your knowledge of your region/city, assess your region/city's promotion of digital tools to improve product traceability according to the following statements:

1	High improvement is needed: Minimal support exists for digital tools enhancing product traceability. Industries have low adoption of EU-level digital passports, and their availability in the region/city is insufficient, hindering effective traceability.	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	Improvement is needed: Efforts are underway, but fragmented. Adoption of EU-level digital passports is sporadic among industries, and regional availability varies. Alignment with EU standards improvement for reliable traceability.	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	Moderate implementation: Moderate support exists for digital tools. Some industries adopt EU-level digital passports, improving traceability. Efforts to ensure regional/city availability and align with EU standards require enhancement.	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	Good implementation: Effective promotion and implementation of digital tools. Many industries use EU-level digital passports, enhancing traceability. Regional availability is established, with ongoing alignment to EU standards for consistency.	<input type="checkbox"/>
5	Excellent implementation: Outstanding promotion and adoption of digital tools. Most industries use EU-level digital passports, ensuring robust traceability. Tools are widely available regionally and fully comply with EU standards, enabling seamless product tracking.	<input type="checkbox"/>

Self-reflection exercise: based on your previous answer, complete the following box in order to improve your region's/city's readiness to adopt Circular Economy practices concerning the use of digital tools to improve product traceability.

Barriers/ Challenges	Enablers/ Facilitators
Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.	Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.
Measures to overcome the barriers/ challenges and actions to enhance enablers/facilitators	
Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.	

CAPACITY BUILDING DIMENSION

Capacity of the education system to meet the challenges of the Circular Economy.

 HINT Which elements could configure or enhance the region/city's educational system capacities?:

- *Comprehensive Curriculum Development: Development and integration of curricula that focuses on Circular Economy principles, sustainable practices, and green technologies across all educational levels;*
- *Implementation of policies that promote the inclusion of Circular Economy education in schools, colleges, and universities;*

- *Development of accreditation and certification systems to recognize and validate educational programs that focus on the Circular Economy;*
- *Existence of training by sectors;*
- *Knowledge exchange between regions that are more advanced in CE training.*

Based on your knowledge of your region/city, please assess your region/city's education system capacities according to the following statements:

1	High improvement is needed: The educational system lacks comprehensive curriculum development focusing on Circular Economy principles. Policies to promote Circular Economy education are absent, and there are no accreditation or certification systems. Sector-specific training and knowledge exchange with advanced regions are non-existent.	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	Improvement is needed: The educational system has some initiatives related to Circular Economy education, but they are limited and underdeveloped. Policies exist but are not effectively implemented. Accreditation and certification systems are minimal, and sector-specific training and knowledge exchange are sporadic.	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	Moderate implementation: The educational system moderately addresses Circular Economy challenges. There is some curriculum development and policy support, with a few accreditation and certification programs. Sector-specific training is available, but not widespread, and there is some knowledge exchange with regions/cities with a stronger educational system.	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	Good implementation: The educational system effectively supports Circular Economy education with well-developed curricula, strong policy support, and several accreditation and certification programs. Sector-specific training is available and accessible, with regular knowledge exchange initiatives with advanced regions.	<input type="checkbox"/>
5	Excellent implementation: The educational system excels in preparing for Circular Economy challenges. Comprehensive curricula, robust policies, and extensive accreditation and certification programs are in place. There is abundant sector-specific training, and the region actively engages in knowledge exchange with other advanced regions.	<input type="checkbox"/>

Self-reflection exercise: based on your previous answer, complete the following box in order to improve your region's/city's readiness to adopt Circular Economy practices concerning the capacity of the education system to meet the challenges of the Circular Economy.

Barriers/ Challenges	Enablers/ Facilitators
Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.	Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.
Measures to overcome the barriers/ challenges and actions to enhance enablers/facilitators	
Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.	

Balanced match between labour supply and demand for Circular Economy industries in the region/city.

 HINT Which elements could configure or enhance a balanced match between labour supply and demand?:

- *Effective vocational training education adapted to the companies needs and promotion of the dual Vocational Education and Training (VET);*
- *Public private partnership and competence centres are in place;*
- *Effective knowledge transfer between universities and companies/industries;*
- *Enhanced capacity building through targeted training programs for the unemployed and active employment policies.*

Based on your knowledge of your region/city, assess the match between labour supply and demand for Circular Economy industries in your region/city according to the following statements:

1	High improvement is needed: There is a significant mismatch between labour supply and demand for Circular Economy industries. Vocational training is not aligned with industry needs, public-private partnerships and competence centres are absent, knowledge transfer is minimal, and targeted training programs for the unemployed are lacking.	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	Improvement is needed: There are some efforts to match labour supply with demand for Circular Economy industries, but they are insufficient. Vocational training is partially aligned with industry needs, public-private partnerships and competence centres exist but are not fully effective, and knowledge transfer and targeted training programs are sporadic.	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	Moderate: The region/city demonstrates moderate alignment between labour supply and demand for Circular Economy industries. Vocational training is somewhat aligned with industry needs, there are several public-private partnerships and competence centres, knowledge transfer is moderate, and there are some targeted training programs for the unemployed.	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	Good implementation: The region/city effectively matches labour supply with demand for Circular Economy industries. Vocational training is well-aligned with industry needs, strong public-private partnerships and competence centres are in place, knowledge transfer between universities and industries is robust, and there are effective targeted training programs for the unemployed.	<input type="checkbox"/>
5	Excellent implementation: The region/city excels in matching labour supply with demand for Circular Economy industries. Vocational training is comprehensively aligned with industry needs, extensive and highly effective public-private partnerships and competence centres are in place, knowledge transfer is continuous	<input type="checkbox"/>

	and highly effective, and targeted training programs for the unemployed are abundant and highly successful.	
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Self-reflection exercise: based on your previous answer, complete the following box in order to improve your region's/city's readiness to adopt Circular Economy practices concerning the match between labour supply and demand for Circular Economy industries in the region/city.

Barriers/ Challenges	Enablers/ Facilitators
Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.	Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.
Measures to overcome the barriers/ challenges and actions to enhance enablers/facilitators	
Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto.	

Annex 2: Mind-map: grey literature results

¿Cuál es la situación actual de estas dimensiones con respecto a la EC?

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101036838.

Annex 3: Regional stakeholder panel workshop results

Agro2Circular

**Outcomes Workshop –
Circular economy model for
the Region of Murcia –
July 7, 2023**

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101036838.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101036838.

Outcomes Workshop –Circular economy model for the Region of Murcia - July 7, 2023

In the workshop held on July 7, 2023, the results of the survey were presented to the stakeholders of the region and the Murcia partners of the Agro2Circular project. This survey asked for each of the eight established dimensions about the level of agreement (Likert scale from 1 to 5) with different items (challenges) identified in the region of Murcia in each of the dimensions, as well as their relevance for the adoption of the Circular Economy. The workshop’s objective was to know first-hand the participants’ opinion about the results and validate with them the model’s generalization through the decontextualization of the statement of the items.

Diagnosis / validation (outcomes) Adoption, replication and scalability

The survey is divided in 8 dimensions:

1. ENVIRONMENTAL
2. SOCIOECONOMIC
3. GOVERNANCE
4. REGULATION
5. FINANCIAL
6. STANDARIZATION
7. TRAINING
8. TECHNOLOGY AND R + D

ENVIRONMENTAL DIMENSION

Comments on the Diagnosis of the Environmental Dimension:

- > Secondary commodities market:
 - There is not yet a legal market for secondary raw materials. Products derived from secondary raw materials cannot yet be certified
 - There is the problem of wastes decommission.
- > Soil contamination:
 - There are areas in the Region with highly contaminated soils, but it should not be generalised to the entire Region.
 - The challenge of soils is not only their contamination but that they are threatened and that they are of low quality.
- > For the rest of the items presented :
 - Water resources, quantity and treatment of waste, channels for reuse and revaluation, and educational programs and awareness: there was a consensus on the results presented and no comments or discussions were made.

PROPOSALS FOR ACTION ENVIRONMENTAL DIMENSION

In the workshop, the idea of creating a market for secondary raw materials was transmitted, but first, the challenge of decommissioning waste would have to be solved.

SOCIOECONOMIC DIMENSION

LACK OF CONSENSUS ON THE VALIDITY OF THE FOLLOWING CHALLENGES:

CHALLENGES WITH THE HIGHEST LEVEL OF AGREEMENT:

Comments on the Diagnosis of the SocioEconomic Dimension:

- Corporate culture:
 - There is no incentive for CE in the companies themselves.
 - Companies tend to prioritize economic profit. But there are already companies for which environmental considerations are also essential since some companies understand that in the long term, it is a benefit.
- Training in CE and sustainability:
 - The university has a vital role in green training.
 - The training programs from school must/should train on CE and sustainability and that these concepts are internalized.
 - The problem of education is a state problem. Companies that have green/energy initiatives are sometimes the ones that have to promote training initiatives at the university.
- Enterprise size:
 - Very small companies find it much harder to invest in CE.
 - A frame of reference and support is needed. Large companies indeed have a greater capacity for CE than small companies.
- Qualified personnel:
 - It is estimated that in the Region of Murcia, there are sufficient qualified personnel to apply the principles of the CE.
 - Training (both university and professional) is essential for the circular economy.

PROPOSALS FOR ACTION SOCIO-ECONOMIC DIMENSION

Training on CE and sustainability from school to increase awareness on the subject.

Increase the role of the university in green/EC education.

Create a framework of reference and support on small and medium-sized enterprises.

TECHNOLOGICAL DIMENSION

LACK OF CONSENSUS ON THE VALIDITY OF THE FOLLOWING CHALLENGES:

CHALLENGES WITH THE HIGHEST LEVEL OF AGREEMENT:

Comments on the Diagnosis of the Technological Dimension:

- Microenterprises reluctant to R+D:
 - Small companies are limited in their ability to innovate because it requires a lot of financial resources.
 - Institutions play a key role, especially due to the large number of SMEs: for green energy and CE and advising on the available subsidies/grants. The public sector has to coordinate its actions with a medium and long-term vision.
 - Companies interested in Innovation have channels to carry it out, the scale and results of innovation.
- Weight EU aid:
 - The success rate of European project applications is quite low. Small businesses do not have resources to dedicate to them.
- Research/company relation:
 - There is no such public-private collaboration throughout the university. This is directly related to the size of the departments. In general, there is little transfer in CE and sustainability.
 - The promotion of the RIS3 will be key to supporting the leading sectors.
 - We must make these issues more attractive to ordinary citizens. We must understand citizenship as the group of users of this type of project.

PROPOSALS FOR ACTION TECHNOLOGICAL DIMENSION

Fund more university chairs in CE by companies.

Improve the dissemination/communication of existing funds for the CE and the projects being funded.

FINANCIAL DIMENSION

Comments on the Diagnosis of the Financial Dimension:

- Lack of disclosure of funding funds:
 - There is a need for public outreach about funding..
 - There are already many lines of support (CDTI), but there is a need in the INFO for a well -endowed concrete line on CE, for SMEs.
 - One challenge is that as ERDF funds are highly sectorized, it is difficult to finance comprehensive projects.
 - Small businesses have to rely on agencies that know the about available funds; technological centres are crucial.

PROPOSALS FOR ACTION FINANCIAL DIMENSION

Regional television outreach programme on funding opportunities and funded projects.
 Better coordination of funding opportunities
 Specific and well -resourced line on CE oriented to SMEs.

STANDARIZATION DIMENSION

Comments on the Diagnosis of the Standarization Dimension:

- Standards dedicated to the circular economy:
 - Standards dedicated to the circular economy are necessary. Creating a working group for a protocol to produce bioactive compounds would be positive.
 - It is necessary to define the requirements for the END OF WASTE: there are some requirements, and those requirements are not yet defined; this could be part of a regulation.
 - There are already waste managers who sell waste to producers, but there are no standards or regulations on this regard.
 - With standardization and regulation, there would be more companies in the sector.
- Challenges:
 - Traceability is important for marketing: waste is not always the same during the year; it changes seasonally. This is a challenge as the final product has to meet several standards.
 - The import into the EU of products without traceability that don't follow several standards.
 - Inclusion of CE products in public procurement.

PROPOSALS FOR ACTION STANDARIZATION DIMENSION

Establishing a working group to create a protocol for producing marketable bioactive compounds.
 Incorporate products derived from CE in public procurement.
 Improve the traceability of by -products to support CE.
 Better define requirements.

GOVERNANCE DIMENSION

LACK OF CONSENSUS ON THE VALIDITY OF THE FOLLOWING CHALLENGES :

CHALLENGES WITH THE HIGHEST LEVEL OF AGREEMENT:

Bodies for the circular economy governance

• Not very valid • 2 • 3 • 4 • Very valid

Availability of the CE Strategy

• Not very valid • 2 • 3 • 4 • Very valid

Metropolitan governance

• Not very valid • 2 • 3 • 4 • Very valid

Lack of transparency

• Not very valid • 2 • 3 • 4 • Very valid

Lack of dialogue and private actors' representation

• Not very valid • 2 • 3 • 4 • Very valid

Funding role

• Not very valid • 2 • 3 • 4 • Very valid

Comments on the Diagnosis of the Governance Dimension:

- Bodies for the governance of the CE:
 - The main public actors responsible for CE policies are the regional government and municipalities. There are no intermediate institutions.
- Availability of the CE Strategy:
 - The current Regional CE Strategy addresses the problem of lack of transparency and inoperability.
 - Effective implementation, monitoring, and impact assessment mechanisms are essential.
- Metropolitan governance:
 - The absence of a metropolitan governance of the Circular Economy in the Region constitutes a serious obstacle and also the lack of a "metropolitan governance culture", due to the size of the urban area and, also, to the different municipalities' population heterogeneity in this Region.

PROPOSALS FOR ACTION GOVERNANCE DIMENSION

Strategies and plans must be effectively implemented, monitored, and evaluated.
 CE initiatives in rural areas should be supported.
 CE criteria should be included in the balance sheet of companies

REGULATORY DIMENSION

LACK OF CONSENSUS ON THE VALIDITY OF THE FOLLOWING CHALLENGES :

CHALLENGES WITH THE HIGHEST LEVEL OF AGREEMENT:

Absence of specific legislation on CE in the region of Murcia

• Not very valid • 2 • 3 • 4 • Very valid

National legislation facilitates CE in the region of Murcia

• Not very valid • 2 • 3 • 4 • Very valid

Food Waste Law

• Not very valid • 2 • 3 • 4 • Very valid

Non-compliance with CE legislation

• Not very valid • 2 • 3 • 4 • Very valid

European regulation facilitates CE in the region of Murcia

• Not very valid • 2 • 3 • 4 • Very valid

Green Procurement

• Not very valid • 2 • 3 • 4 • Very valid

Comments on the Diagnosis of the Regulatory Dimension:

- Food Waste Act:
 - The Law on food waste and its potential effects on the Circular Economy in the Region is currently being processed in the Spanish Senate, so it is not possible to comment about this until the configuration of the law and its effective application.
- Lack of influence in the regulatory process:
 - Certain complexity in terms of the influence that citizens, and even significant actors such as companies, can exert in the European regulatory process.
- Specific Law on Circular Economy for the Region of Murcia:
 - A specific waste law or circular economy, adapted to the local peculiarities of the production system and the different value chains of Murcia, would be essentially beneficial for the region.
 - The current legislation promoting the Circular Economy is not fully implemented.
- Other conclusions:
 - Local products from the region of Murcia are affected by the demands of international regulations, in particular by the completeness of Globalization; the need for Global regulations, and competitiveness issues with imported food products which are not required to accomplish with these regulations.
 - The Possibility of Local Strategies: local strategies can be implemented to favour products that meet certain circular economy requirements
 - Influence of the EU Taxonomy: The EU products will be required to follow that taxonomy to receive funding.

PROPOSALS FOR ACTION REGULATORY DIMENSION

Education and Citizen Awareness.
 Improving stakeholder participation in regulatory processes.
 Improving stakeholder participation in regulatory processes.
 Review and compliance with Current Legislation.
 Protection of Local Products.
 Promotion of Global Traceability Standards or Certifications.
 Improving the Competitiveness of Local Products.
 Development of Local Circular Economy Strategies.
 Implementation of the EU Taxonomy.
 Incorporation of International Trade Rules into Local Regulation

TRAINING DIMENSION

RELATIVE CONSENSUS ON THE VALIDITY OF THE FOLLOWING CHALLENGES:

CHALLENGES WITH THE HIGHEST LEVEL OF AGREEMENT:

Specific training by sector

• Not very valid • 2 • 3 • 4 • Very valid

Vocational training for the unemployed

• Not very valid • 2 • 3 • 4 • Very valid

Other active employment policies

• Not very valid • 2 • 3 • 4 • Very valid

Private training resources

• Not very valid • 2 • 3 • 4 • Very valid

Public university offer

• Not very valid • 2 • 3 • 4 • Very valid

Educational curriculum

• Not very valid • 2 • 3 • 4 • Very valid

Comments on the Diagnosis of the Training Dimension:

- > Large availability of private resources:
 - There is an identified gap between the available knowledge and its actual application in the business world, which indicates the need to encourage the effective use of these private resources for the transition to the circular economy..
- > Little public offer of university training in circular economy:
 - There is a perception of delay in adapting university education to the current demands of transition towards a more sustainable economy. The training problem is not exclusive to Murcia but extends to the whole country and is even a problem throughout Europe.
- > The primary, secondary, and baccalaureate curricula in the Region of Murcia include circular economy content in a satisfactory way, but there is no information regarding the actual application of these curricula:
- > Deficit of vocational training programmes adapted to the various sectors of occupation sectors in the circular economy (number of courses and course quota).
- > Insufficient vocational training programs for the unemployed in the Region of Murcia (number of courses and quota per course).
 - Increasing awareness of the usefulness and career opportunities of the circular economy in all productive sectors is considered essential to foster the demand for this training.
- > Lack of other active employment policies (e.g., career guidance) for the circular economy:
 - There is a disconnect between what is offered in terms of training and what companies really need. Participants highlight the importance of dual training.

PROPOSALS FOR ACTION TRAINING DIMENSION

- Encourage environmental awareness from the basic educational level.
- Integrate environmental issues into the academic curriculum.
- Strengthening university and professional education on circular economy.
- Promote convergence between training and demand in the productive sector.
- Encourage the uptake of dual VET in enterprises.
- Increase social awareness on CE.

Annex 4: European stakeholder panel workshop results

Outcomes Workshop –EU Stakeholders- May 10, 2024

In this workshop, we aim to explore how the dimensions and components of the Regional Model for Circular Economy in the Agrofood sector, developed in the Region of Murcia as part of the Agro2Circular initiative, can be adapted and applied to other European regions.

We examined various dimensions to assess the relevance of the model's elements and identify any additional components that should be incorporated. It is important to emphasize that these insights will play a key role in refining and validating the model, as well as in developing a self-assessment tool designed to assist regions in their transition toward a circular economy in the agrofood sector.

This workshop's aim is to validate the relevance of the A2C circular model at regional level that have been created enabling the transferability to other EU regions and the development of a self-assessment tool

ENVIRONMENTAL DIMENSION

- Efficient waste and water management:**
The region has implemented infrastructures to increase the efficiency of waste and water management.
- Waste valorisation channels:**
There are channels that allow the valorisation of waste inside the region, allowing certain value chains to be closed and narrowed
- Territorial exploitation level:**
The region is able to satisfy the demand of raw materials fostering synergies between industries and avoiding conflicts between land functions (agriculture, industry, urban, natural use)
- Land degradation processes:**
There is a proportion of land suffering degradation processes in the region as a consequence of inadequate waste management, including pollution, reduction of soil fertility or erosion.
- Carbon footprint**
In the region, there are measures to assess and reduce the carbon footprint of the existing value chains

Indicate, from your point of view, the relevance of the following statements:

ENVIRONMENTAL DIMENSION KEY IDEAS

- EFFICIENT MANAGEMENT
- CLIMATE CHANGE
- OVERRATED TERMS BY POLITICS

Comments on the Diagnosis of the Environmental Dimension:

Carbon footprint was the item with the lowest score, this is due to two reasons: in principle the participants consider it to be overrated, especially in the political scene, and it is also integrated in the rest of the items.

> WHICH ITEMS DO YOU THINK IS MISSING? **Biodiversity Biogeochemical cycles**

SOCIOECONOMIC DIMENSION

- Business reinvention capacity**
Businesses are able to adopt and transform sustainably in response to the challenges and opportunities present in the region, with the aim of promoting local economic, social and environmental development.
- Professional and technical skills related to the CE**
The regional labour force skills are adequate and sufficient for a transition from a linear to a circular model.
- Trust in the productive system**
Confidence and reliance that the regional stakeholders have in the efficiency, fairness, and sustainability of the local economy and its related industries.
- Regional cultural aspects**
Beliefs, values, traditions, and behaviours of a specific geographic area that influence citizens attitudes and actions towards sustainable consumption, production, and waste management practices.
- Circular economy citizenship participation**
Promotion of initiatives (bottom-up) awareness campaigns at city/ regional level for the reduction of waste, return schemes for packaging, sharing models.

Indicate, from your point of view, the relevance of the following statements:

**SOCIOECONOMIC DIMENSION
KEY IDEAS**

CITIZEN'S TRUST IN ECOSYSTEM
TECHNICAL SKILLS IN TRANSITION
SIZE OF INDUSTRY

Comments on the Diagnosis of the Socioeconomic Dimension:

- Cultural aspects are considered and prioritized so as **citizenship participation** In regions where there are a strong ecosystems and people are working together, and they are engaged. Those things are going very smoothly where is not a clear ecosystem, even though the drive from public institutions.
- Specific **technical skills** the participants affirm that it is not so necessary such an investment in skills for some figures needed. But it's a **transition**: low skilled people and mediumly skilled people can achieve.
- The **size of industry** is a determinant aspect for business or invention capacity. That's clear that the biggest company generates the biggest pollution. The biggest company are the ones which have potential more money, but they are no changing so fast because that's quite complicated and expensive. There are a lot of small companies. It is quite difficult to convince them to work together, so there are too many factors just to say it's a big that will be complicated.

GOVERNANCE DIMENSION

- Promotion of circular economy culture and trust enhancement**
The regional government promotes circular economy culture and enhance trust (openness and transparency).
- Dialogue promotion in the decision-making process**
Dialogue promotion between the stakeholders and representation of private sector in the decision-making process.
- Existence of specific bodies for the governance of the Circular Economy**
Establishment of "Local Circular Economy Councils" with innovative character, advisory functions, control and transversal participation.
- Existence and implementation of an effective multi-level governance**
Presence and successful operation of governance structures and mechanisms across multiple levels of government, as well as collaboration between various stakeholders, to facilitate the transition towards circular economy.
- Adoption of a functional approach**
Holistic view through a systematic approach at the regional level.
- The region orchestrates, facilitates, promotes and enables the circular economy transition through a wide range of actors and/or political sets.**

Indicate, from your point of view, the relevance of the following statements:

**GOVERNANCE DIMENSION
KEY IDEAS**

HOLISTIC VIEW
PUBLIC AND PRIVATE
COLLABORATION
TRUST
EFFECTICIENT CONCEPT
EFFECTIVE ESTRATEGY

Comments on the Diagnosis of the Governance Dimension:

- The **holistic view** through a systematic approach at the regional level received a very high rate and all participants agree with this concept.
- The governance structure should be highly public, but **public-private partnerships** should be promoted within governance.
- There are positive facts like: a good dialogue, a holistic view, a good adaptation, but there is no trust. And this is necessary to achieve an **effective C.E**
- **Ecoefficient** is a "must" at the governance dimension.
- **Collaborative platform** for the governance of a circular economy, so a proactive team going to try to less different companies and universities and so on, collaborate on the territory

POLICY AND REGULATORY DIMENSION

Indicate, from your point of view, the relevance of the following statements:

POLICY AND REGULATORY DIMENSION KEY IDEAS

EXTENDED PRODUCER RESPONSABILITY

ABILITY TO QUANTIFY

DIGITAL PASSPORT

Comments on the Diagnosis of the Policy and Regulatory Dimension:

- It is not possible to demonstrate the actual recycling content. Consequently, any regulations established are ineffective if we cannot quantify and verify this content. Therefore, while it may seem like a minor detail, the ability to quantify is crucial for the effective implementation of legislation.
- The extended producer responsibility is a key issue.
- A digital passport or certificate will be necessary for food and health products.

FUNDING & FINANCIAL DIMENSION

Indicate, from your point of view, the relevance of the following statements:

FUNDING & FINANCIAL DIMENSION KEY IDEAS

TAXES / PRIVATE FUNDING

INCUBATION PROGRAMS

ECOSYSTEM

BIO ECONOMY

Comments on the Diagnosis of the Funding & Financial Dimension:

- Finance-related questions involves numerous subelements. Considering the public sector, higher taxes are needed on undesirable activities in Europe, as changes are not occurring rapidly enough. Additionally, the role of public procurement, which has not been previously emphasized, serves as a significant catalyst for both public and private finance.
- The agrofood sector is relevant for all of us; for citizen, for the Community is not only business, and the companies still now are considering that just a business.
- While social impact is a welldefined category, circular economies lack this distinction: there is a lot of social impact funds, but there are no circular impacts: Incubation programs are needed and a developing community for impact finance (Bio economy).

STANDARIZATION DIMENSION

STANDARIZATION DIMENSION KEY IDEAS

DIGITAL TOOL
TRACEABILITY
VALUE CHAIN

Comments on the Diagnosis of the Standarization Dimension:

- A tool can be for example to self evaluate your potential as the one we are using this passport. Can be a tool that for traceability you can know you as consumer can know all the pathway of the material along the value chain.

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